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Value Chain and System Development – Hydrogen component manufacturing readiness and spatial requirements

D4c.1 – Supply chain risk management approach for hydrogen infrastructure components

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Technology and Safety

- Activities (e.g. maintenance, purging etc.)
- Assets
- Digitalisation
- End use
- Gas network
- QRA

Social aspects

- Conversion (of the distribution network)
- Education
- Social

System and Economy

- Business Development
- Production and supply
- Value chains

Gas Quality

- Admixing
- Gas Quality
- Odourisation

Summary

Hydrogen gas is expected to become an essential clean energy carrier in the Netherlands and globally. The introduction and scaling of hydrogen systems face numerous challenges, including market dependencies, supply chain complexities, and resource limitations.

Many stakeholders in a future hydrogen system, from hydrogen production (upstream) via transportation, distribution and storage (midstream) to end-users (downstream), require physical components in the near future. The ability of those component supply chains to supply the components in time can thus be considered preconditional for the realisation of a hydrogen system.

The study explores supply chain risks related to component manufacturing, highlighting that disruptions in the supply chain can significantly delay the completion of the hydrogen system. Procurement strategies and asset lifecycle management are directly affected by the size and orientation of suppliers in the global market. As stakeholders with a business model focussed on asset management typically rely heavily on external component suppliers, managing risks associated with procurement becomes essential. Questions regarding which components may suffer from disruptions, how many components are needed, and whether manufacturing lead times are compatible with the project timeline are central to ensuring project delivery on schedule.

The result of this study is a supply chain risk management approach that can be used by many different stakeholders in the hydrogen system. And as the timely and successful realization of infrastructure projects is crucial to connect supply, demand and storage, the approach is tested with case studies and examples of potential bottlenecks in the hydrogen transport and distribution infrastructure and end-use component manufacturing supply chain. The findings reveal several insights into the maturity, scalability, and vulnerability of the hydrogen component supply chain, and how these factors might impact the successful realization of hydrogen projects.

Supply chain readiness directly affects the ability to meet project milestones. For example, delays in critical components like compressors, essential for hydrogen transport, distribution and storage, can severely hinder project timelines when insufficiently managed. Additionally, long lead times for permitting, regulatory approvals, and detailed engineering processes are other potential obstacles. Therefore, risk identification and mitigation in procurement activities are crucial to prevent supply chain delays from becoming limiting factors.

The output of this study is a five-step Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) approach to identify and mitigate supply chain risks. This approach aims to contribute to the timely availability of critical components required in construction projects.

The steps include:

1. Identifying component needs
2. Analysing trade flows and manufacturing industry characteristics
3. Consulting Original Equipment Manufacturing and supply chain experts
4. Performing risk assessments
5. Translating procurement and supply chain risks into the critical path planning of infrastructure development projects.

The research highlights the growing complexity of supply chain planning, especially when considering multiple interconnected infrastructure projects that make up a broader hydrogen transport network.

The key finding from this study therefore is the importance of early-stage and continuous supply chain risk management to prevent component supply issues from hindering project timelines.

Throughout the execution of these five steps, four methods or tools are applied: scenario planning (step 1), stakeholder consultation (step 3), risk assessment (step 4) and critical path planning (step 5). In addition, generative AI software is applied to gather manufacturing industry characteristics.

The SCRM approach is tested by means of two component case study deep-dives from an infrastructure point of view and one end-use component case:

- hydrogen gas compressor for compression of large volumes of gas up to 200-300 bar
- hydrogen flow meter
- hydrogen burner system

The selected case study supply chains for compressor, flow meter and burner system demonstrate that these existing supply chains are ready to scale up further and have little vulnerabilities regarding sourcing, routing and flow volume. The flow destination and value density (i.e., compliancy to quality demands) does require mitigation actions to reduce the supply chain risk levels from those perspectives.

Four recommendations are proposed to enhance the availability of hydrogen components through their manufacturing supply chains:

- **Apply the SCRM approach:** Capital intensive hydrogen project developers are encouraged to apply the SCRM approach developed in this study to real-world projects to validate the effectiveness of the approach and adopt organisation-specific improvements to existing component supply chain strategies. Continuous monitoring and updating of the approach will allow for the early identification of risks and timely mitigation.
- **Enrich existing ways of working with the new insights presented:** The current supply chain strategies of organisations serve as the foundation of any improvement that is to be considered. The added value of adopting the risk-based supply chain framework and strategies should be assessed based on the current practices to pave the way for effective improvements.
- **Develop explicit risk mitigation strategies for low-TRL components:** Stakeholders in up, mid and downstream activities should craft explicit supply chain risk strategies and take proactive measures to reduce their dependency on component supply chains with lower-technology readiness. Collaborative research and development programs, along with upfront investments in manufacturing capacity for key components, can help mitigate supply risks.
- **Expand on this approach with more components and services:** Future research into and development of this approach should aim to include a broad range of hydrogen components and also include infrastructure development services to provide a more comprehensive understanding of relative supply chain vulnerabilities.

By adopting these recommendations, stakeholders can strengthen their ability to manage supply chain risks, ensuring the successful and timely deployment of hydrogen infrastructure. This is critical to achieving the Netherlands' hydrogen transition goals and advancing the energy transition in the Netherlands, Europe and globally.

Samenvatting

Waterstofgas wordt verwacht een essentiële schone energiedrager te worden in Nederland en wereldwijd. De introductie en opschaling van waterstofsysteemen staan echter voor diverse uitdagingen, zoals marktafhankelijkheden, complexiteit in toeleveringsketens en beperkingen in grondstoffen.

Veel betrokken partijen in een toekomstig waterstofsysteem – van productie (upstream) via transport, distributie en opslag (midstream) tot eindgebruikers (downstream) – hebben op korte termijn fysieke componenten nodig. De beschikbaarheid van deze componenten op het gewenste moment in de tijd is daarmee een randvoorwaarde voor de realisatie van een waterstofsysteem.

Dit onderzoek verkent risico's in toeleveringsketens gerelateerd aan de productie van componenten. Het toont aan dat verstoringen in deze ketens de oplevering van een waterstofsysteem aanzienlijk kunnen vertragen. Inkoopstrategieën en asset life-cycle management worden direct beïnvloed door de schaalgrootte en marktrichting van leveranciers op de wereldmarkt. Aangezien organisaties met een bedrijfsmodel gericht op assetmanagement doorgaans sterk afhankelijk zijn van externe leveranciers, is het essentieel om inkoop- en toeleveringsketenrisico's te beheersen. Centrale vragen hierbij zijn: welke componenten risico lopen op verstoringen, hoeveel van deze componenten zijn nodig zijn, en sluiten de levertijden aan bij de gewenste projectplanning?

Het resultaat van deze studie is een risicomanagementbenadering voor toeleveringsketens die door verschillende belanghebbenden binnen het waterstofsysteem kan worden toegepast. Omdat het tijdig en succesvol realiseren van infrastructuurprojecten cruciaal is om waterstofvraag, aanbod en opslag met elkaar te verbinden, is deze aanpak getest met casestudies en voorbeelden van potentiële knelpunten in de toeleveringsketens van waterstoftransport, distributie en eindgebruikerscomponenten.

De bevindingen geven inzicht in de volwassenheid, schaalbaarheid en kwetsbaarheid van toeleveringsketens van waterstofcomponenten, en hoe deze factoren het tijdig realiseren van waterstofinfrastructuur projecten beïnvloeden. Een voorbeeld is dat vertragingen in kritieke componenten zoals compressoren – essentieel voor transport, distributie en opslag – verregaande gevolgen kunnen hebben voor de projectplanning als de risico's hierop niet voldoende worden beheerd. Daarnaast kunnen lange doorlooptijden voor vergunningen, regelgeving en het technisch ontwerpen tot veel vertraging leiden. Het identificeren en beheersen van risico's in de inkoopactiviteiten is daarom van cruciaal belang om vertragingen in toeleveringsketens te voorkomen.

De uitkomst van deze studie is een vijfstappenaanpak voor risico identificatie en mitigatie in toeleveringsketens (Supply Chain Risk Management, SCRM). De aanpak beoogt hiermee om bij te dragen aan het tijdig beschikbaar maken van kritieke waterstofcomponenten voor constructieprojecten:

1. Identificeren van benodigde componenten.
2. Analyseren van handelsstromen en kenmerken van de maakindustrie.
3. Raadplegen van fabrikanten en experts in toeleveringsketens.
4. Uitvoeren van risicoanalyses.
5. Vertalen van inkoop- en toeleveringsketenrisico's naar een kritieke pad planning voor infrastructuurprojecten.

Tijdens deze stappen worden vier methoden of tools toegepast: scenarioplanning (stap 1), stakeholderconsultatie (stap 3), risicoanalyse (stap 4) en kritieke pad planning (stap 5). Daarnaast wordt generatieve AI-software gebruikt om kenmerken van de maakindustrie te verzamelen.

De SCRM-aanpak is getest via drie diepte analyses voor de volgende componenten:

- Een waterstofcompressor voor het comprimeren van grote volumes gas tot 200-300 bar.
- Een waterstofstroommeter.
- Een waterstofbrandersysteem.

Deze casussen laten zien dat de bestaande toeleveringsketens voor deze componenten klaar zijn voor verdere opschaling en weinig kwetsbaarheden vertonen op het gebied van leveranciersselectie, logistiek en productievolumes. Wel vereisen de bestemming van de componenten en de waardedichtheid (bijvoorbeeld het voldoen aan kwaliteitseisen) mitigerende acties om de geïdentificeerde risico's te verminderen.

Vier aanbevelingen worden gedaan om de beschikbaarheid van componenten via de maakindustrie ketens te stimuleren:

- **Pas de SCRM-aanpak toe in projecten:** Ontwikkelaars van kapitaalintensieve waterstofprojecten worden aangemoedigd om deze aanpak te gebruiken en organisatie-specifieke verbeteringen toe te voegen. Continu monitoren en bijwerken van de aanpak maakt tijdige identificatie en beheersing van risico's mogelijk.
- **Verrijk huidige werkwijzen en strategieën met nieuwe inzichten:** Bestaande inkoop en toeleveringsketen beheersstrategieën vormen de basis voor de gesuggereerde nieuwe verbeteringen. De meerwaarde van risicogestuurde ketenstrategieën moet worden beoordeeld en geadopteerd in relatie tot bestaande praktijken.
- **Ontwikkel expliciete risicostrategieën voor laag-TRL componenten:** Stakeholders in up-, mid- en downstreamactiviteiten moeten proactief maatregelen nemen om afhankelijkheid van componentketens met een lage technologische gereedheid te verminderen. Samenwerking in R&D-programma's en investeringen in productiecapaciteit kunnen hierbij helpen.
- **Breid toekomstig onderzoek uit met meer componenten en diensten:** Het verder ontwikkelen van de aanpak moet een breder scala aan waterstofcomponenten omvatten, evenals diensten voor infrastructuur-ontwikkeling, om een meer omvattend beeld van ketenkwetsbaarheden te geven.

Door deze aanbevelingen te volgen, kunnen belanghebbenden beter omgaan met risico's in de toeleveringsketen, waardoor naar de tijdige uitvoering van waterstofinfrastructuurprojecten wordt toegewerkt. Dit is cruciaal voor het behalen van de waterstofdoelen van Nederland en het bevorderen van de energietransitie in Nederland, Europa en wereldwijd.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The context and research questions of this study

Hydrogen is envisioned to have a central role in the energy and feedstock transition in many regions around the world, and North Western Europe specifically. Its successful deployment is essential not only for meeting climate goals but also for maintaining the competitiveness of industrial activities of various sectors in the Netherlands, amongst which the chemical, fuels and steel sector.

Much of the existing research on hydrogen focuses on its operational stages — such as intermediate and end-use applications within energy systems, including energy distribution and industrial consumption. Only limited attention has thus far been given to the availability of physical equipment and components needed. This gap in research highlights the need for the exploration of the level of risk associated with those component supply chains and how to secure a timely availability. To meet the ambitious target of a fully deployed hydrogen system, stakeholders must deliver many projects upstream supply (hydrogen production), midstream infrastructure (transportation, distribution and storage) and downstream consumption (end-use). Together, the sum of those projects form the hydrogen system.

Commonalities amongst capital intensive hydrogen projects include long planning horizons, complex coordination across multiple public and private stakeholders, and public procurement procedures to acquire the technological components needed. These components, sourced from a range of international suppliers, must be delivered and integrated according to the project schedule. However, hydrogen technologies can currently be considered niche technologies that are expected to upscale substantially in the near future. Those manufacturing supply chains therefore will face supply chain risks, including supplier shortages, geopolitical tensions, extended lead times, and limited production capacity for critical items. The complexity of modern supply chains, particularly in large infrastructure projects, introduces vulnerabilities that can lead to substantial delays. Examples of supply chain questions that arise in hydrogen-related projects are:

- Which components are most at risk of disruption?
- How many different components are required, and which stakeholders consider them critical?
- When are components needed, and how will potential supply chain delays affect project timelines?
- Can original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) scale up production in time to meet demand?
- Are current lead times, with risk-based minimum-maximum buffers, acceptable given the overall project timeline?

Addressing these questions requires not only traditional supply chain management but also the application of advanced risk management frameworks. A core contribution of this research is the development of a method for the early identification and mitigation of supply chain risks. By applying this method to three components, we demonstrate how stakeholders can proactively manage risks and secure timely delivery of critical components, ultimately reducing the potential for project delays.

The objective of this study is to assess the component manufacturing supply chain readiness for hydrogen-related technologies to be used in Dutch projects. By identifying barriers and bottlenecks in scaling the component supply chain, the study aims to propose practical measures that can minimize project delays. These results will contribute to ongoing efforts by capital intensive hydrogen project developers to manage component supply chain risks and ensure timely project execution.

More specifically, this research focuses on three research questions:

1. How mature, scalable, and resilient can hydrogen component manufacturing supply chains be expected to be?
2. What consequences can these component supply chain characteristics have on the procurement process of public hydrogen projects?
3. What specific actions can stakeholders take to mitigate component supply risks to ensure the timely availability of crucial components?

Parts of the hydrogen system are public infrastructure systems, amongst which are the transport and distribution systems and centralized storage. The timely realization of hydrogen infrastructure will facilitate the adoption of clean hydrogen as a critical energy carrier across a variety of existing and future applications, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable and resilient energy future. However, the introduction and scaling of hydrogen within energy and feedstock systems presents numerous challenges, many of which are both foreseeable and unforeseeable (also see HyDelta 2.0, D3.3¹). At the current critical preparation phase of hydrogen infrastructure rollout, understanding uncertainties and mitigating risks is essential.

As public infrastructure has a facilitating role connecting supply and demand development of hydrogen, the pace of the hydrogen system development is highly dependent on the timely availability of that public infrastructure. This study therefore includes case study deep-dives on two transmission infrastructure components and their supply chain risks: large volume hydrogen compressors and flow meters. In addition, the hydrogen burner technology supply chain for hydrogen end-use applications was analyzed. And a high level reflection on various components required for public distribution infrastructure was done.

1.2 Research method and work flow

Given the complex nature of supply chain risks, addressing them effectively requires a multifaceted approach. In this study, we applied the following research methods to comprehensively assess and manage supply chain risks:

Figure 1 The five-step approach to assess supply chain risk in project planning

These steps are explained in more detail below:

1. **The Need for Components:** The first step is to establish a clear understanding of the amount of necessary components over time, and identifying those that may be critical for a hydrogen technology-based project. The availability of certain essential components, such as compressors,

¹ TNO, [D3.3 Individual and system uncertainties in hydrogen value chain developments \(zenodo.org\)](https://zenodo.org/records/7811111), 2023

can directly impact project timelines, necessitating early engagement with suppliers and a comprehensive demand forecasts.

2. **Component Trade Flow Analysis:** This step helps stakeholders analyze the international flow of components and key variables affecting supply chains. Factors such as market share, firm reliability, and production capacity must be assessed to anticipate potential delays or disruptions. This stage allows for the quantification of risks based on country, firm and component-level data, factoring in elements such as production capacity globally and trade relations between the Netherlands and the countries in which the manufacturing supply chains are located.
3. **OEM and SCM Expert Consultation:** Engaging directly with Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and Supply Chain Management (SCM) experts is crucial for developing an informed perspective on component and manufacturing readiness. Such consultations ensure that data and information gathered is validated.
4. **Risk Assessment:** Building on the previous steps, a structured risk assessment can identify and quantify vulnerabilities within the supply chain by means of the Supply Chain Vulnerability Index consisting of many individual variables developed in this study. This assessment integrates supply chain risks into project planning to pinpoint which component supply chain characteristics are most likely to cause delays or affect project success.
5. **Component Procurement on the Critical Path:** Finally, integrating the risk assessment into the overall (level one) project timeline is vital to illustrate the vulnerability of the overall project success to well-managed supply chain risks. Procurement strategies should focus on ensuring that critical components are acquired in time to keep the overall project on track. By understanding which components and procurement activities are on the "critical path"—those without which the project cannot move forward—stakeholders can prioritize procurement decisions accordingly.

We report the outcomes of this research at two levels:

1. **Generalized methodological approach:** This offers a structured framework that can be applied broadly across various hydrogen infrastructure projects, providing stakeholders with a systematic approach to identifying and mitigating supply chain risks.
2. **Typical theoretical project examples and component case studies:** These case studies demonstrate how the generalized methodology can be practically applied, using specific examples such as hydrogen compressors, burners, and flow meters. This shows real-world applications of the framework and provides insights into how it can be adapted to address unique challenges in future projects.

Note: The majority of the examples focusses on public infrastructure project development. However, the topics discussed and insights gained can be generalized as the majority is also applicable and relevant to upstream and downstream stakeholders and their projects.

1.3 Report structure and reading guide

To assess the component supply risks we first need to understand the type of components needed as part of a future hydrogen system, the characteristics of those technologies and the characteristics of the manufacturing supply chains. These topics are discussed in **Chapter 2**. By using a hydrogen system breakdown structure (2.1), we zoom in on three component case studies (2.2) and the use of existing energy system scenarios we estimate the number of those components in 2030, 2040 and 2050. The subsequent manufacturing market analysis sketches the current manufacturer landscape (2.3-2.5). These component demand projections set the scene for the research on manufacturing supply chain readiness and the underlying supply chain risk assessment.

A large number of greenfield and brownfield hydrogen infrastructure projects need to be realized. **Chapter 3** discusses the complexity of large infrastructure projects by a public operator to put this component manufacturing supply chain assessment in the right context. Four topics are discussed: The challenges associated with megaprojects (3.1), an example timeline for a public infrastructure project and the procurement activities that are part of such a project (3.2), the public procurement framework on which these procurement activities need to be based (3.3) and the introduction of *critical path analysis*, a key ingredient to merge risk management with project planning.

The successful realization of projects depends on having the required component available at the right time. Delays in procurement activities and/or supply chain related issues can be problematic when they become substantial. **Chapter 4** discusses in detail how we built on existing risk management approaches to meet the objective of this research. In paragraph 4.1 we introduce risk management in relation to supply chain management. And in subsequent paragraphs the classical steps of a risk assessment are discussed in more detail with a focus on component availability: Risk identification (4.2), Risk prioritization (4.3), Risk mitigation (4.4). In paragraph 4.5 the risk assessment insights are translated to project planning insights.

And **Chapter 5** deepens the understanding and application of the Supply Chain Risk Management approach by exploring three scenarios: The supply chain risk increase in case of a lower technological readiness level (TRL) of a component (5.1), the impact on supply chain risks when the number of suppliers turns out to be lower than expected (5.2) and the effect of taking multiple complementing risk mitigation strategies to lower the risk score (5.3).

A discussion of strengths and limitations of the results on a methodological and a typical project level are found in **Chapter 6**, accompanied by the conclusions and recommendations of this study.

2 Hydrogen components required and their characteristics

To assess the component supply risks we first need to understand the type of components needed as part of a future hydrogen infrastructure, the technical characteristics of those components and the characteristics of the manufacturing supply chains.

By using a hydrogen system breakdown structure (2.1), defining three component case studies (2.2) and the use of existing energy system scenarios we estimate the number of types of components required. And subsequent manufacturing market analysis sketches the current manufacturer landscape (2.3-2.5). These component demand projections set the scene for the research on manufacturing supply chain readiness and the underlying supply chain risk assessment.

2.1 Hydrogen system and breakdown structure

The Netherlands is actively working on creating a hydrogen value chain as part of their comprehensive energy transition initiative. Establishing the necessary infrastructure to connect hydrogen production with consumer markets is a crucial element in the development of this value chain. The choice of systems for the hydrogen value chain will vary, depending on the specifics of supply and demand, including their volumes and geographic locations. Each chosen system comprises multiple components, and the interfaces between these systems and the midstream systems referred to in this report as *infrastructure* are illustrated in the figure 2 below.

Hydrogen system breakdown (incl. scope of infrastructure)

Figure 2 Hydrogen system breakdown

In this research, a system breakdown structure (SBS) is employed to examine the various segments within the hydrogen value chain systems. An SBS is an organized depiction that outlines both the functional and physical portions of a system, ranging from the overall system down to its individual components. Utilizing an SBS is instrumental in defining a system's scope, limitations, connections, and interdependencies. Figure 3 illustrates the hierarchical structure of the hydrogen value chain systems, where each system consists of several subsystems, and each subsystem consists of several components.

The components are the smallest units that can be procured from vendors and integrated into a subsystem. The subsystems are the functional groups of components that perform a specific task within a system. Examples of subsystems are underground gas storage, pipeline transportation, and industrial end use. The systems are the integrated sets of subsystems that enable the production, storage, distribution, and utilization of hydrogen. Examples of systems are central production with offshore storage, decentralized production with onshore storage, and direct supply to industry.

In this study, the focus is on the component level of the hydrogen value chain systems, as this level provides the most detailed and actionable information for supply chain management. The components are the building blocks of the hydrogen systems and have direct implications for the cost, performance, reliability, and safety of the systems. Moreover, the components are subject to various supply chain risks and opportunities, such as market dynamics or technological developments. Therefore, it is important to assess the characteristics, requirements, and challenges of each component and identify the best practices and strategies for their procurement, installation, operation, and maintenance.

The subcomponent level, which refers to the internal parts of the components, such as drive shafts, engines, electronics, or even (rare) materials used, is out of scope for this study. Based on expert judgment, it is not expected that the suppliers of component manufacturers will introduce new types of risk. Rather, the risks at the subcomponent level are likely to magnify those already present at the component and system levels, such as supply chain disruptions or quality issues. Therefore, focusing on the component level allows us to address the most critical risks relevant to the entire hydrogen system.

Figure 3 A selection of the Hydrogen System Breakdown (focus of the case studies highlighted in green)

2.2 Selected use-cases

Among the numerous components that constitute the hydrogen value chain systems, three were selected as case studies for the implementation of supply chain management. These components are:

- **Compressors with an application in hydrogen storage in salt caverns.**

Compressors are devices that increase the pressure of hydrogen gas to enable its storage or transportation through pipelines. They are essential for the underground gas storage system, which is one of the options for storing excess hydrogen produced from renewable sources.

- **Fiscal flow metering applied in (inter)national transport and regional distribution pipeline networks.**

Fiscal metering is the process of measuring the quantity and quality of hydrogen transferred between different stakeholders in the value chain, such as producers, transporters, and consumers. It is an important interface that ensures the accuracy, transparency, and accountability of hydrogen transactions.

- **Hydrogen burner systems as part of high temperature heat facilities.**

High temperature heating is a technology that uses hydrogen as a fuel to generate heat for industrial processes, such as chemical industry, or ceramics manufacturing. It is one of the potential end uses of hydrogen in industry, which can reduce greenhouse gas emissions and increase energy efficiency.

The selection of these three components as case studies was based on the results of the scoping phase of HyDelta. During this phase, initial interviews were conducted with various stakeholders involved in the project. The interviews revealed the main challenges and opportunities related to the supply chain management of hydrogen systems and helped identify the most relevant and critical components for further analysis. It should be noted that during the execution of the project, other components were also recognized as having significant supply chain risks, such as offshore pipeline installation. However, since the purpose of this research is to demonstrate the methodology and framework for assessing the supply chain risks and opportunities of hydrogen systems, the same approach can be applied to any other component in the future.

To anticipate future scenarios for different hydrogen systems, capacity ranges were analyzed within the context of spatial planning considerations². These ranges encompass the probable fluctuations and uncertainties related to future hydrogen availability and utilization, embodying varied strategies to realize energy transition objectives. By calculating the quantity and variety of necessary components for each potential system, the expected costs, practicality, and overall implications linked to the hydrogen value chain systems can be deduced.

The scenario's provided in the I13050 study³ form the base of our estimation of the number of types of components. The I13050 study is a comprehensive and strategic research effort designed to guide the Netherlands through its energy transition up to the year 2050. Conducted by Netbeheer Nederland, the study examines various pathways for the Dutch energy system, considering different approaches to decarbonization, the role of hydrogen, and the necessary infrastructure to achieve national and European climate targets. The scenarios within the study provide critical insights into potential future energy systems, each with distinct policy directions, technological advancements, and economic factors. These scenarios are instrumental for stakeholders in planning and preparing for the diverse supply chain and infrastructure needs that may arise under different future conditions.

The I13050 study gives the capacity of hydrogen production and use on a system level, based on four possible pathways for the Dutch energy transition: A) Decentral initiatives, B) European integration, C) National leadership, and D) International trade. Each scenario has different assumptions and implications for the role of hydrogen in the energy system and the corresponding supply chain requirements. For example, scenario A has the lowest hydrogen demand and the highest share of green hydrogen, while scenario D has the highest hydrogen demand and the lowest share of green hydrogen. The other scenarios are somewhere in between, with varying degrees of blue and turquoise hydrogen production. Based on these scenarios, we can derive the range of possible capacities and numbers of components for each hydrogen system. In addition, the three scenarios of the Investment Plans (IP2024⁴) of the Dutch DSO are also included in the analysis: Climate ambition (KA), National incentives (ND) and international ambitions (IA). The envisioned capacity in these scenarios are shown in the figure 4 below.

Note that I13050 scenarios illustrate plausible future energy system designs that may also transform differently with much higher or lower amounts of hydrogen gas. This may result in higher or lower amounts of components in the hydrogen system.

² R. Detz et al "D4c.2– Spatial requirement contours of hydrogen projects" HyDelta, 2024.

³ Netbeheer Nederland, Het energiesysteem van de toekomst: de I13050-scenario's, 2023

⁴ Netbeheer Nederland, IP2024 scenario rapportage, 2023

Figure 4 Hydrogen supply and demand scenarios (Source: IP2024 and II3050)

2.3 Case study: Hydrogen gas compressor 60 to 200-300 bar

2.3.1 Hydrogen storage in salt caverns

Salt caverns are artificially created cavities built in salt deposits. They are suitable for the storage of liquid hydrocarbons and in particular for gases under high pressure. Large amounts of gas can safely be stored due to large geometrical volumes and high storage pressures, thereby creating flexibility for the matching of demand and supply.

Depending on the cavern depth, pressures of 200 bar and above are common. Geometrical volumes reaching up to more than 1 million m³ can be constructed. The special properties of rock salt guarantee the long term stability and gas tightness of the cavities, when operated within suitable pressure ranges. Compared to other underground excavations very low specific construction costs are achieved because creation and operation of the caverns is done from above ground through usually only one single well bore, which is equipped with special piping and equipment. No technical installations are required underground except for this well.

Energystock (subsidiary of Gasunie) operates the natural gas storage facility in Zuidwending. At this facility, natural gas is stored in salt caverns. The caverns have geometric volumes ranging between 600,000m³ and 1,000,000 m³, and are equipped with 2 wells, which allows for high injection and withdrawal rates. Above-ground facilities consist of electrical compressors, to compress the gas from its pipeline pressure of 60 bar to a storage pressure of max. 180 bar, ventilators to cool down the gas, and dryers to dry the moist gas after withdrawal from the caverns prior to reinjection into the grid. Above-ground facilities for hydrogen storage will be similar but may require additional gas cleaning equipment to clean the hydrogen gas that is withdrawn from the cavern to a pre-defined purity level for injection into the backbone.

The storage capacities of a typical cavern of 1,000,000 m³ geometric volume vary between 215GWh and 252GWh (LHV). Hydrogen has already been successfully stored in salt caverns in UK and the US for long periods of time and therefore appears feasible within short term in Europe.

Gas caverns are normally operated by compression and decompression between a minimum and a maximum pressure (sliding pressure method). Thus the gas inventory can be divided into working gas, which can be withdrawn from the cavern during normal operation, and cushion which must remain in the cavern to ensure its stability. Roughly estimated, about one third of the gas inventory is required as cushion gas, depending on the geology, depth, and other parameters. When injecting and withdrawing the gas, the operational pressure of the storage varies between the aforementioned pressure limits.

2.3.2 Compressors for salt caverns

At the gas cavern a compressor is needed to compress the incoming gas to inject it into the underground storage. This is typically up to a pressure of up to 150-200 bar depending on type and depth of underground gas storage.

Reciprocating compressors utilize pistons to compress gas within a chamber through reciprocating motion. They are generally suitable for lower flow rates and high-pressure differentials, making them efficient for hydrogen compression in small-scale applications or when precise pressure control is required. However, they tend to have higher maintenance needs due to their intricate mechanical design. In contrast, centrifugal compressors leverage rotating impellers to accelerate gas, increasing its velocity before converting it into pressure through diffusion. These compressors excel in high-flow, low-pressure ratio scenarios, offering continuous operation and lower maintenance requirements compared to reciprocating compressors.

Moreover, reciprocating compressors typically have higher efficiency at lower flow rates and can handle varying inlet conditions better, while centrifugal compressors are more efficient at higher flow rates and offer a more compact design. The choice between them depends on factors like required pressure ratio, flow rate, footprint constraints, and maintenance considerations, with each offering advantages tailored to specific hydrogen compression applications. For applications on gas cavern storage, the low molar weight of hydrogen combined with the pressure requirements, often the use of a volumetric or reciprocating compressor is preferred over a centrifugal one.

In this case study, we describe the compressors and their manufacturers available on the market and explore the supply chain risks.

Figure 5 Hydrogen Compressor (Source; Howden⁴)

2.3.3 Number of compressors

Based on the scenarios described above, the required capacity of caverns in the Netherlands ranges from 5 PJ/year in 2030 to 61 PJ/year in 2050. A typical salt cavern is assumed to have a capacity of 0.9 PJ/cavern. This leads to 6 to 68 caverns required for hydrogen storage, depending on the demand and supply situation and development in time. The number of caverns can be reduced by increasing the pressure range or the volume of each cavern, but this may entail additional technical and economic challenges. The location and availability of suitable salt formations for cavern development is also an important factor that needs to be considered.

Figure 6 Estimated hydrogen storage capacity in salt caverns

Assuming two compressors per salt cavern, this leads to the number of compressors as depicted in Figure 7 below. The figure shows the range of compressors needed for different scenarios of hydrogen demand and supply in the Netherlands, from low to high. As the figure illustrates, the number of compressors increases significantly with higher hydrogen demand and lower domestic production.

Figure 7 Estimated number of compressors at salt caverns

2.3.4 Supply chain risks for compressors

The interviews with suppliers and experts have provided various insights into the risks and opportunities for the deployment of compressors in the hydrogen chain. The main insights are:

- **R&D trajectories and long-term purchase guarantees.** One of the main challenges for the delivery of compressors is the need to start R&D trajectories to make the technology suitable for hydrogen. This requires upfront investments from both the client and the contractor, which are not without risk. A possible solution is to conclude agreements as soon as possible that offer a long-term purchase guarantee, so that the contractor can justify the R&D investment.
- **Standardization and scale benefits.** Another insight is that the delivery of compressors can be faster, cheaper and more qualitative if more standardization and scale benefits are achieved. This applies to both new and existing technologies. Purchasing multiple identical components makes engineering and production more profitable and results in a shorter delivery time. The use of existing technologies, such as lubricated compressors, reduces the uncertainty and complexity of the design and production.
- **Specific bottlenecks and competitive advantages.** Finally, some specific bottlenecks and competitive advantages have been identified for the delivery of compressors. A bottleneck is the availability of electric motors for large compressors, for which there are only a limited number of suppliers. Another bottleneck is the capacity for testing new technologies on a full scale.

Based on an internet survey using large language models, an overview of compressor manufacturers was made in which 20 manufacturers were listed. The company names are included below and the detailed overview is included in Appendix A. summarized in the table below. The market scope and size of the companies is used in the risk assessment in Chapter 4.

Table 1 Compressor manufacturers

Company Name	Size	Company Name	Size
Atlas Copco	Large	Mitsubishi Heavy Industries	Large
Burckhardt Compression	Large	Fornovagas	Medium
Haskel	Medium	Bumhan Industries	Medium
Ingersoll Rand	Large	Howden Group	Large
Bauer Compressors	Large	Kaji Technology	Large
ABC Compressors	Small	Xi'an Shaangu Power	Large
Aerzen	Medium	Gardner Denver Nash	Large
Siemens	Large	HAUG Sauer Kompressoren AG	Medium
Hydro-Pac	Small	NEUMAN & ESSER GROUP	Large
Ingersoll Rand A/S	Large	Endress+Hauser AG	Large

2.4 Case study: Hydrogen metering

2.4.1 Hydrogen meters

In the gas industry, the methods for transporting, measuring, and billing natural gas through pipelines are thoroughly established. There are comprehensive ISO standards and ongoing improvements to procedures that support these activities, ensuring effective transport and custody transfer. For those activities, gas flow meters have been in use for decades. Flow meters are required for hydrogen transport activities.

Technically the availability of (large scale) hydrogen meters is not a major obstacle for the development of the hydrogen market. Several manufacturers who are currently active in the natural gas industry have already developed meters that are suitable for hydrogen applications. These meters are operationally suitable, i.e., can be used without malfunction, and (safety) approvals in place, but from a metrological point of view, the technologies are not proven for accuracy and reliability when measuring hydrogen, this only holds for natural gas.

Figure 8 Flow Meter (Source; Krohne⁵)

Re-using existing natural gas meters for hydrogen is not a viable option, as there are significant differences in the physical properties and flow behaviour of the two gases. For instance, hydrogen has a lower density, higher compressibility, and higher diffusivity than natural gas, which can affect the performance and calibration of the meters. Therefore, hydrogen meters need to be designed and certified specifically for hydrogen use, following the relevant standards and regulations.

2.4.2 Meter calibration

With decarbonization ambitions moving forward, the transport of hydrogen is becoming increasingly important to facilitate the transition to renewables. Like natural gas infrastructure, precise measurement systems for hydrogen are essential to ensure compliance with national and international regulations.

⁵ [Flow measurement for the drinking water supply in the City of Emden | KROHNE Group](#)

The trade in hydrogen will involve an increasing number of stakeholders in the near future, necessitating accurate measurement and calibration systems traceable to national and international standards. However, there is currently no complete hydrogen flow metrology framework available for these gases, signalling a need for significant research and development in this area.

Those efforts need to pave the way for flow meter manufacturers to adjust existing and/or develop products designed specifically for the hydrogen trade. Although a fully-fledged market for hydrogen trading and calibration is not yet in existence, it is anticipated to expand within the next 3 to 6 years. Given the essential role of metering, the preparation should start now to be able to meet industry demands with refined metrology and metering solutions by that time. Taking into account that a complete hydrogen flow metrology framework with the necessary reference values and standards takes time, the lack of traceability can turn into a bottleneck.

Hydrogen metering systems need to be assessed under all gas conditions along the hydrogen value chain and at the lowest possible uncertainty. This requires calibration of flow meters at gas test facilities accredited for their entire quality system with traceability as an important item.

The hierarchy below and accompanied explanation introduces the order in which metrology developments typically mature:

- I. SI
- II. National standards (NMI)
- III. Accredited calibration facilities
- IV. In-house calibration
- V. Measurement equipment

Primary standards are developed and maintained in a country by its *National Metrology Institute* (NMI, in the Netherlands this role is fulfilled by VSL). The NMI is appointed to establish the link to the *SI international units of measurement* of its primary standards. NMIs from different countries work closely together to ensure that the lowest uncertainties in reference values are achieved.

Typically, methods exist that enable to transfer the traceability from the NMI's primary standard to external (calibration) facilities. This will lead to an *accredited facility* capable of performing calibrations with a defined measurement uncertainty with a claimed Calibration and Measurement Capability (CMC). The calibration facility should obtain the ISO17025 accreditation under specified H₂ conditions. Currently, there are no primary standards for hydrogen gas flow units applicable to gas transmission networks, posing a technology barrier. The claimed uncertainty should be sufficiently small to be acceptable within the industry, i.e. comparable to natural gas standards. A prerequisite for completing the activities described above is national and international agreement on the required accuracy for performance measurements of hydrogen gas flow meters and how this should be demonstrated.

After establishing the calibration facility's traceability and metrics for repeatability, reproducibility, and uncertainty, certification processes for various metering technologies can commence at a large(r) scale via *in-house calibration* and the subsequent production of *measurement equipment*.

2.4.3 Number of fiscal meters

Based on the scenarios mentioned in the previous section, we estimated the number of fiscal meters to be scaling with the length of the hydrogen infrastructure pipeline. The hydrogen infrastructure pipeline consists of production, transmission, distribution and end-use segments, each with different pressure, temperature and flow conditions. The fiscal meters need to measure the quantity and quality of the hydrogen gas at various points along the pipeline, such as production sites, interconnection points, injection points, exit points and delivery points.

It was assumed that the average distance between two fiscal meters is 50 km. This implies that the number of fiscal meters is proportional to the total length of the hydrogen pipeline network. According to the scenario's depicted in the figure 9 below, the planned length of the network ranges from 0 to 3000 km for the regional transport system (RTL) and from 1100 to 1360 for the high pressure transport grid (HTL). The length is divided by 10 km to obtain the number of fiscal meters. This number is a rough estimate, for high pressure pipeline systems, the number of connections might be lower, for RTL it might be higher. This results in an estimated total number of meters in the order of 110 to 440.

Figure 9 Estimated pipeline length

Figure 10 Estimated number of hydrogen flow meters

2.4.4 Supply chain risks for metering

Interviews were conducted with the meter manufacturers and VSL, the National Metrology Institute of the Netherlands, to identify the main supply chain risks related to calibration. The main findings are:

- **Technology readiness:** The technology for fiscal metering of hydrogen gas is not the bottleneck. Most manufacturers have existing or adapted products that can measure hydrogen gas with acceptable performance ranges. The main challenge is to ensure traceability to the SI units of measurement and comparability of the measurements across different locations and countries.
- **Standardization under development:** In order to validate the accuracy and reliability of the fiscal meters, they need to be calibrated with a reference standard traceable to the SI units of measurement. However, the necessary calibration standards for hydrogen gas are not yet available (in metrological sense) and harmonization will be the next step.
 - o The calibration standards for hydrogen transmission gas flow are under development. VSL has a primary gas flow standard for hydrogen refilling stations available and is working on developing a primary standard for high pressure hydrogen gas flow, which will serve as the reference for secondary standards and calibration facilities. However, this process will take several years and requires international collaboration and validation.
 - o For determination of gas quality there are reference standards available to calibrate the analysers and these standards provide these measurement instruments with traceability.
 - o The lack of calibration standards for hydrogen gas flow poses a risk for the development and deployment of the fiscal meters, as well as for the establishment of a transparent and fair market for hydrogen. Without a common and accepted reference, the fiscal meters may not be accepted by the parties involved in the transactions, and disputes may arise over the quantity and quality of the delivered hydrogen. This may hinder the growth and competitiveness of the hydrogen sector in the Netherlands and Europe.

Based on an internet survey using large language models, an overview of flow meter manufacturers was made in which over 50 manufacturers were listed. The company names are included below and the detailed overview is included in appendix A. summarized in the table below. The market scope and size of the companies is used in the risk assessment in chapter 4.

Table 2 Flow meter companies

Company Name	Size	Company Name	Size
Aalborg	Large	Flow Meter Group	Medium
ABB	Large	Fluid Components International (FCI)	Large
ABLE Instruments	Medium	Fuji Electric	Large
Acorn Controls	Medium	Hitachi High-Tech	Large
Acorn Controls Private Limited	Medium	Horiba	Large
Action Instruments SA	Medium	Keyence	Large
Afrox	Large	KOBOLD	Large
Alicat Scientific	Medium	Kofloc	Medium
Aman Engineering Works	Medium	KROHNE Group	Large
ANZIGA	Medium	Manas Microsystems	Medium
ATO Flow Meter	Medium	Mass Flow ONLINE	Medium
Azbil	Large	MATHESON	Large
Azbil Corporation	Large	McCrometer	Large
Badger Meter	Large	Omega Engineering	Large
Baker Hughes (Panametrics)	Large	Panametrics	Large
Bronkhorst	Medium	Prism Instrumentation	Medium
Brooks Instrument	Large	Rheonik	Large
Burak Metering	Medium	Sensirion	Medium
Chart Industries	Large	SICK	Large
Creative Engineers	Medium	Siemens	Large
ELIS PLZEN	Medium	Sierra Instruments	Large
Elster-Instromet	Large	Sunflow Technologies	Medium
Emerson	Large	Swagelok	Large
Emerson AU	Large	TotalEnergies	Large
Endress+Hauser	Large	TRICOR Coriolis Technology	Large
Energas Technologies	Medium	Turbines, Inc.	Large
Energoflow AG	Medium	Yokogawa	Large
FLOMEC	Medium		

2.5 Case study: High temperature burner systems

2.5.1 Hydrogen for high temperature heating

The ceramics, glass and process industries are at a crossroads, exploring hydrogen as a sustainable alternative for high-temperature heating amidst global decarbonization efforts. The ceramics and glass industry, with its dispersed and remote operations, faces unique challenges in integrating hydrogen, including technical concerns like NO_x emissions and the impact on product quality. The process industry is proactively setting ambitious carbon neutrality targets, with hydrogen as a key component in their strategy. These industries recognize the necessity of pilot projects to address technical challenges and validate hydrogen's feasibility.

A critical aspect underpinning these ambitions is the supply chain's robustness. For the ceramics industry, the remote location of facilities heightens the importance of a reliable hydrogen supply, as any disruption could significantly impact production. In the process industry, the strategic location near potential hydrogen pipelines can offer a competitive advantage, but it also underscores the need for a secure and uninterrupted hydrogen supply. The realization of hydrogen ambitions is contingent upon mitigating supply chain risks, ensuring consistent availability, and managing the transition at acceptable costs without compromising operational continuity or product quality. Blends of hydrogen and natural gas could initially mitigate an interrupted hydrogen supply. Burner systems for high temperature heat for blends or pure hydrogen need to prove their effectiveness with acceptable emissions, on industrial scale.

View on hydrogen for High-Temperature heating in the ceramics and glass industry

The ceramics industry is characterized by fragmentation and a presence in remote locations, often in floodplains away from central infrastructure. This positioning typically places the industry in a lower priority sector for decarbonization initiatives. Current sustainability strategies within the industry aim for significant reductions in energy consumption through process optimizations, with many companies setting goals for the near future, such as a 25% reduction by 2025.

Hydrogen is seen as a potentially interesting option for decarbonization, particularly for high-temperature heating processes in both ceramics and glass industries. However, the industry's familiarity with hydrogen is generally limited, and it is at the early stages of considering how hydrogen could be integrated into existing energy supplies. The main technical concerns regarding hydrogen use include:

- Potential increases in NO_x emissions: Given the sensitive locations of ceramic plants, any increase in NO_x emissions is a critical issue that requires a proven solution.
- Impact on kiln atmosphere and product quality: The addition of hydrogen to the fuel mix could change the kiln atmosphere, affecting the quality of the ceramics produced, an impact that is currently unknown and needs further research.

The industry acknowledges the need for more pilot projects to investigate these issues and develop viable, cost-effective solutions. While there is no consensus on the timing of a potential switch to hydrogen, blending hydrogen with natural gas is considered a logical first step before transitioning fully to hydrogen. However, the industry emphasizes the necessity for additional research to understand the effects of hydrogen on NO_x formation and product quality. The industry's view on hydrogen is cautious but open to exploration, with a clear recognition of the challenges that need to be addressed.

View on hydrogen for High-Temperature heating in the process industry

The process industry is actively exploring pathways to carbon neutrality, with strategic plans targeting dates like 2035. Historically significant consumers of natural gas, these industries are now considering hydrogen as a technically logical solution for decarbonization, especially for high-temperature processes where electrification is not economically viable. Key points in the industry's view on hydrogen are:

- Strategic Decarbonization: Companies are aligning with shared investment agendas to advance decarbonization, although progress varies, particularly among those with international headquarters.
- Alternative Energy Sources: While biogas and electrification are being explored, hydrogen stands out as the most viable long-term solution for main processes, especially where electrification is not feasible due to high costs.
- Pilot Projects: Initiatives like converting thermal oil boilers to hydrogen are crucial for gaining familiarity and assessing the viability of hydrogen in operational settings.
- Investment and Ambition: There is a willingness to invest in becoming frontrunners in hydrogen application, recognizing that a complete switch by 2035 is ambitious, making blending a logical interim step.
- Technical Challenges: Maintaining NOx emissions within legal limits and developing burner technology for hydrogen use are significant challenges. Large-scale pilot projects are needed to address these issues and demonstrate feasibility.
- Infrastructure Considerations: Proximity to potential hydrogen supply routes, such as pipelines, is a strategic advantage for some companies.

In summary, the process industry views hydrogen as a promising option for high-temperature heating, with a cautious yet proactive approach. The industry is calling for more research, development, and pilot projects to overcome technical hurdles and ensure a smooth transition to hydrogen-based processes. The commitment to decarbonization is clear, but the path forward requires careful planning, collaboration, and innovation.

Figure 11 Hydrogen Burners (Source: Elco Burners⁶)

⁶ [Elco Burners - H2 READY BURNERS \(elco-burners.com\)](https://www.elco-burners.com)

2.5.2 Number of high temperature heating systems

Based on the scenarios described above, the required capacity of high temperature heating in the Netherlands ranges from 2000 MW/year in 2030 to over 9000 MW/year in 2050. The number of burners in high temperature heating systems varies for the different applications. For example, in tunnel ovens used for brick production multiple small burners are used in different parts of the oven. Typical capacity per oven is 10 MW with up to 200 burners. In high temperature (chemical) process installations individual burners systems with capacities over 20 MW can be used. To estimate the total number of burners required the assumption is made that the burner system have an average capacity of 10 MW. This results in numbers of systems in the range of ~200 - 900.

Figure 12 Estimated required industrial burner capacity

Figure 13 Estimated number of industrial burners

2.5.3 Supply chain risks for burner systems

The interviews with suppliers and experts have provided various insights into the risks and opportunities for the deployment of high temperature heating systems. The main insights are:

- **Technical Readiness:** Successful trials have shown that hydrogen can be used as a fuel. Systems capable for using hydrogen – natural gas mixtures ranging from 0 to 100% hydrogen have been demonstrated. These systems require adaptation of the control system or even replacing the burner. However, scaling up power and maintaining low NOx emissions remains a challenge.
- **Supply Chain Readiness:** Suppliers are preparing for the transition to hydrogen. The lead time for delivering a gas burner, regardless of the gas type, is expected to be between 2 to 9 months. For larger capacity and special products, the longer lead time is due to specific engineering. The supply chain management system is designed to have alternatives in place to mitigate risks. Long-term relationships with suppliers and open communication help in managing potential delays.
- **Policy and Regulation:** The transition to sustainable fuels like hydrogen is uncertain due to the current reliance on natural gas, which is available and affordable. Companies are hesitant to invest in alternative fuels until there is clarity and consistency in policy, availability, and affordability of sustainable fuels. Clear and consistent policies are crucial for the supply chain to prepare adequately.

Based on an internet survey using large language models, an overview of burner manufacturers was made in which over 20 manufacturers were listed. The company names are included below and the detailed overview is included in appendix A. summarized in the table below. The market scope and size of the companies is used in the risk assessment in Chapter 4.

Table 3 Burner system manufacturers

Company Name	Size	Company Name	Size
Air Liquide	Large	Industrial Combustion	Large
Babcock & Wilcox	Large	Instalat	Medium
Bloom Engineering	Medium	John Zink Hamworthy	Large
E&M Combustión	Medium	Maxon (Honeywell Company)	Large
Ecostar Burners	Medium	Monarch	Large
Elco Burners	Large	Osaka Gas	Large
ESA Pyronics International	Medium	Rinnai Corporation	Large
Faber Burner Company	Large	SGD Pharma	Large
Fives Group	Large	Stork Thermeq	Large
Forney Corporation	Large	Tokyo Gas	Large
Honeywell UOP	Large	Zantingh	Medium
Hyundai Heavy Industries	Large	Zeeco Inc.	Large

3 Energy infrastructure asset management, project planning and public procurement

To meet their goal of a fully deployed hydrogen system, a large number of complex capital intensive hydrogen technology projects need to be realized. We can refer to such projects as a megaproject, including all the challenges and solutions that relate to such project.

To put this component manufacturing supply chain assessment in the right context we introduce three key topics in this chapter: The challenges associated with megaprojects (3.1), infrastructure asset management and the associated public procurement activities that are part of such a project (3.2), and the introduction of *critical path analysis*, a key ingredient to merge risk management with project planning (3.3).

3.1 Many hydrogen projects are megaprojects with associated challenges

Megaprojects are “*large-scale, complex ventures that typically cost a billion dollars or more, take many years to develop and build, involve multiple public and private stakeholders, are transformational, and impact millions of people*”⁷. Typically, when projects of this size go wrong, whole companies and national economies suffer.

Megaprojects have characteristics that set them apart from smaller, more comprehensible, projects. These characteristics, summarized below⁸, are typically overlooked which has dire consequences for the successful execution of the project(s).

- Megaprojects are inherently risky due to long planning horizons and complex interfaces.
- Often projects are led by planners and managers without deep domain experience who keep changing throughout the long project cycles that apply to megaprojects, leaving leadership weak.
- Decision-making, planning, and management are typically multi-actor processes involving multiple stakeholders, public and private, with conflicting interests
- Technology and designs are often non-standard, leading to "uniqueness bias" amongst planners and managers, who tend to see their projects as singular, which impedes learning from other projects.
- Frequently there is overcommitment to a certain project concept at an early stage, resulting in “lock-in” or “capture,” leaving alternatives analysis weak or absent, and leading to escalated commitment in later stages. "Fail fast" does not apply; "fail slow" does.
- Due to the large sums of money involved, principal-agent problems and rent-seeking behavior are common, as is optimism bias.
- The project scope or ambition level will typically change significantly over time.
- Delivery is a high-risk, stochastic activity, with overexposure to so-called "black swans," i.e., extreme events with massively negative outcomes. Managers tend to ignore this, treating projects as if they exist largely in a deterministic Newtonian world of cause, effect, and control.
- Statistical evidence shows that such complexity and unplanned events are often unaccounted for, leaving budget and time contingencies inadequate.
- As a consequence, misinformation about costs, schedules, benefits, and risks is the norm throughout project development and decision-making. The result is cost overruns, delays, and benefit shortfalls that undermine project viability during project implementation and operations.

⁷ Flyvbjerg, [What You Should Know About Megaprojects and Why: An Overview](#), *Project Management Journal* – Wiley Online Library, 2014

The result of projects with those characteristics is as striking as it is painful: only 0.5% of the megaprojects are delivered on time, on budget and in accordance with the envisioned benefits⁹. The graph below from another study¹⁰ is an illustration of cost overruns and delays for infrastructure, mining and oil and gas projects.

Figure 14 Illustration of typical megaproject cost overrun and delays

The root causes of these underperforming projects identified in the study are summarized below. The majority do relate fully, or partially, to manufacturing supply chains and the procurement activities of infrastructure projects:

Factors that cause cost overruns and delays and with a direct relation to supply chain management and procurement:

- **Poor organization.** Decision-making and procurement processes do not have the speed and scale required.
- **Inadequate communication.** Inconsistencies in reporting mean that subcontractors, contractors, and owners do not have a common understanding of how the project is faring at any given time.
- **Contractual misunderstandings.** The procurement team typically negotiates the contract, and this is almost always dense and complicated. When a problem comes up, project managers may not understand how to proceed.
- **Missed connections.** There are different levels of planning, from high-end preparation to day-by-day programs. If the daily work is not finished, schedulers need to know—but often don't—so that they can update priorities in real time.

⁹ Flyvbjerg, How Big Things Get Done, 2023

¹⁰ [The construction productivity imperative | McKinsey](#)

Factors that cause cost overruns and delays and with an indirect relation to supply chain management and procurement:

- **Flawed performance management.** Unresolved issues stack up because of lack of communication and accountability.
- **Insufficient risk management.** Long-term risks get considerable consideration; the kinds that crop up on the job not nearly as much.
- **Poor short-term planning.** Companies are generally good at understanding what needs to happen in the next two to three months, but not nearly so much at grasping the next week or two. The result is that necessary equipment may not be in place.
- **Limited talent management.** Companies defer to familiar people and teams rather than asking where they can find the best people for each job.

We can conclude that successful supply chain management is essential to realise any complex infrastructure project, ranging from energy infrastructure to iconic architecture and bridge infrastructure. The next section dives deeper into the role of procurement in those projects.

3.2 A brief introduction into infrastructure asset management and public procurement

A brief introduction of terminology and information on asset management and public procurement is required to put this study on supply chain risk management in its context of hydrogen transport and distribution system development. This paragraph covers both topics at a high level.

3.2.1 Asset management and asset strategies requires multiple disciplines

Successful asset management, and specifically energy infrastructure asset management, requires a combination of many disciplines in a well-coordinated fashion. The Institute of Asset Management summarizes these connected disciplines well in their diagram below.

Transport and distribution system operators are operating their infrastructure to provide transport services to existing markets and explores new markets. Taking the existing and new markets as a starting point (Commercial environment, in red), the continuous availability and expansion of the physical infrastructure requires, amongst other things, a clear strategic plan at an organisational level, strategy and planning updates, the acquisition of components and continuous interactions of all those plans based on risk and review process insights.

Figure 15 Visualization of the multidisciplinary character of asset management and the interfaces with supply chain risk management (in blue)¹¹

The incorporation of hydrogen transport services to the portfolio will require the organisations to develop and implement asset strategies for those assets and their components. Part of those strategies is the category and procurement strategy.

Category management at an organisational level, and procurement at an infrastructure project execution level, should then enable the acquisition of the hydrogen components in accordance with the requirements of the asset management executives as well as the capabilities of the original equipment manufacturers markets.

The development of new infrastructure assets and the maintenance of existing assets, requires the execution of many construction projects. And in those projects the procurement of components is embedded to acquire the components required. Such a construction project follows a logical flow of activities as is depicted in a project level 1 planning example¹² below.

¹¹ [The Institute of Asset Management - conceptual model of AM](#)

¹² The example is based on a typical onshore infrastructure project. Offshore projects may have their own specifics and were out of scope for this study.

Figure 16 A project level 1 planning overview

Procurement is part of this project (highlighted in red) and we discuss this activity in more detail in the next paragraph.

3.2.2 The public procurement process

Governmental and public sector organisations often need to use open, or public, tender and procurement procedures to purchase the materials or services they require. In this study and the case studies involved, this public procurement process is therefore adopted¹³. The brief introduction below describes what this type of procurement entails.

A public procedure starts with a contract notice (via TenderNed) in the EU Official Journal. This invitation to tender includes the requirements set by the purchaser. The procedure has one round, in which all tenderers (bidders submitting a tender) can submit a tender directly. The purchaser assesses the tenderers and the bids (offers) simultaneously. A tenderer must comply with any suitability requirements set. No grounds for exclusion may apply to them. You award the contract on the basis of (1) the best price-quality ratio, (2) the lowest price, or (3) lowest cost based on cost-effectiveness. If the purchaser does not choose (1) best price-quality ratio but one of the other two basis for awarding the contract, this choice must be justified in the tender documents. Negotiation is not allowed.

Pianoo defines 21 steps¹⁴ as part of the procurement procedure. In this study we bring these steps back to six steps. The table below describes those steps.

Note that variations on the described procurement process can be used as long as they fit in the regulatory framework of public procurement.

¹³ Procurement can also be done through non-open (non-public) processes. This is considered out of scope due to the context of public infrastructure development of this study.

¹⁴ [Fase 2: Doorlopen aanbestedingsprocedure | PIANOo - Expertisecentrum Aanbesteden](#)

Table 4 procurement procedure steps

Pianoo process sequence	HyDelta SCRM process sequence
Preparing the order (including 12 substeps)	Market survey
Announcement	
Registration	Request for tender subcontractors
Selection	
Tendering	
Awarding	Final investment decision (FID)
Finalize	
Execution of the order (including 3 substeps)	Design and procure
	Factory acceptance test (FAT)
	Logistics

The public and transparent nature of this process has clear advantages and disadvantages. Those disadvantages can turn into risks and project delays when ineffectively managed (see Chapter 4).

Table 5 (Dis)advantages of public procurement

Advantages of public procurement	Disadvantages of public procurement
A lot of competitive pressure on tenderers	Strictly described procedure, little freedom in designing the procedure
The whole market can tender	Reasonably long procedure with prescribed minimum deadlines, certainly in relation to national procedures
Objective, transparent and non-discriminatory	Possibly (too) many tenders are submitted
	High procedural costs (partly because of many bids), both for contracting authority and bidders
	No negotiation allowed
	Own experiences with supplier cannot be involved

3.3 Critical path analysis

To answer Research Question 2 (*What consequences can these component supply chain characteristics have on the timely realization of hydrogen infrastructure projects?*), we make use of the risk register and the Critical Path Method (CPM).

CPM is a project management technique to plan, schedule, and manage complex projects. It involves identifying all the tasks needed to complete a project, determining the sequence in which these tasks must be carried out, and then calculating the most prolonged duration of time it will take to complete the project from start to finish. This is known as the ‘critical path’. In our context, understanding how the critical path is influenced by events from the risk register is crucial.

The output of CPM is an overview of the critical paths for the following cases:

- The critical path without risks occurring (the 'base case');
- The critical path with risks occurring but without the application of mitigating measures;
- The critical path with risks occurring , with the application of mitigating measures.

To formulate the critical path and subsequently understand how the critical path is affected by various events from the risk register, we perform the following steps.

3.3.1 Determining the base case

In the first step, we conduct an analysis of a procurement process, creating a 'base case'. This entails identifying the activities involved, their sequence, dependencies, and potential for parallel execution. We translate the standard procurement process into a set of activities with defined durations; where we estimate the minimum and maximum durations for each procurement activity, so that each activity is assigned a maximum "tail" to account for potential delays. We then determine the critical path within the (base case) procurement process.

Figure 17: (Illustrative) overall level 1 project timeline with detailed procurement phase

The estimates for the durations of the activities have been based on information from the interviews. For this study, the focus lies on the procurement of components. Therefore, for the remainder of the study, we zoom in on the 'Procurement of services and materials' phase in the above timeline:

Figure 18: Procurement process timeline

The numbers in this timeline were based on the information received in the interviews. The ranges that were mentioned have been summarized in the table below.

Table 6 Normal duration per procurement process step (source: interviews)

Procurement process step	Compressors [months]	Flow meters [months]	H ₂ burners [months]
1. Market survey	6	6	N/A
2. Request for tender	9-12	9-12	N/A
3. FID	2	2	N/A
4. Design and produce	12-33	12-33	2-9
5. FAT			
6. Logistics			

4 Risk management in supply chains

The successful realization of hydrogen infrastructure projects depends on having the required component available at the right time. And as these components are purchased from suppliers, large delays in procurement activities and/or supply chain related issues can be problematic. Risk management is embedded in projects as a whole, and procurement activities specifically, to prevent those issues and/or minimize the negative effects of on the project realization if risk events fire.

In paragraph 4.1 we introduce risk management in relation to supply chain management. And in subsequent paragraphs the classical steps of a risk assessment are discussed in more detail with a focus on hydrogen infrastructure component availability: Risk identification (4.2), Risk prioritization (4.3), Risk mitigation (4.4). In paragraph 4.5 the risk assessment insights are translated to project planning insights.

4.1 Introducing risk management in context of supply chains

We start by introducing two essential topics: the existing *power asymmetry* between a purchaser and its suppliers, and the *bullwhip phenomenon*.

The purchaser of a component has an essential role crafting the boundary conditions under which a supply chain can function well. In general, a purchaser initiates the transaction and the associated incentive of a supplier and the supply chain in between. The conditions under which the supply chain will develop and supply the purchased good(s) is thereby dictated by the purchaser and the purchaser therefore carries major responsibilities for the performance of supply chain as a whole as there is an asymmetric power distribution. However, in the rare occasions in which there are very few suppliers of a component that is critical to the purchaser, the power balance naturally shifts and suppliers may dictate the conditions under which collaborations are formed.

When demand for components changes, a supply chain of multiple stakeholders will typically respond in accordance with the bullwhip effect¹⁵. The bullwhip effect is a phenomenon where small fluctuations in consumer demand at the retail level lead to progressively larger fluctuations in demand at the wholesale, distributor, manufacturer, and raw material supplier levels. This effect is named after the way a whip's motion amplifies from the handle to the tip, causing significant distortions in the supply chain. This effect leads to supply chain performance issues.

Figure 19 Bullwhip effect illustration showing the over-reacting supply chain stakeholders upstream¹⁶

¹⁵ Forrester, Industrial dynamics, 1961

¹⁶ [\(PDF\) Exploring the Bullwhip Effect and Inventory Stability in a Seasonal Supply Chain \(researchgate.net\)](#)

In supply chains with many stakeholders, each stakeholder can over or underestimate the required product by its purchaser. And the longer the lead times of individual components, or systems as a whole, are, the longer delays of information or goods can propagate through the supply chain and mismatches between supply, demand and available buffer capacities of components can be.

For an individual supply chain stakeholder, ranging from an assembly stakeholder and component-producing specialist all the way to metal and mineral miners, the bullwhip effect can lead to major challenges regarding inventory management, warehousing, transportation and other operational costs as well as labor and machinery capacities required, just-in-time contract compliancy and waste management.

The bullwhip effect is a major challenge for supply chain developments because it amplifies inefficiencies and inaccuracies in demand forecasting, leading to significant disruptions. It causes excessive investments in inventory, lost revenue, and declines in customer service. The effect also makes it difficult to maintain a balance between supply and demand, leading to potential layoffs or bankruptcies. Addressing the bullwhip effect requires improved communication, better demand forecasting, and more integrated supply chain solutions.¹⁷

To minimize the risks associated with the bullwhip effect, supply chain stakeholders on an individual level, and consequently the supply chain as a whole, tend to be risk averse in terms of upscaling production capacities of novel products to minimize potential issues in their business operation. This risk averse behavior underlines the need for risk management in supply chains. Before going into more detail we first introduce the definitions and terminology used in this study¹⁸:

What is a risk? A risk, or risk event, is a single event that has one or multiple causes, a probability of occurrence and can lead to one or multiple effect(s) and subsequent positive or negative consequence(s).

An easy-to-use concept used in risk management is the bowtie diagram (see below). This diagram helps to identify, analyze and prioritize, and mitigate risks by showing the relationships between hazards, their causes, consequences, and mitigation strategies:

One risk event can have many causes (the threats), both foreseeable, unexpected and unknown. And the risk event, when occurring, can have multiple consequences or effects. Risk mitigation strategies can visually be drawn in the bowtie to block threats or consequences and thereby reducing the risk.

¹⁷ <https://www.techtarget.com/searcherp/definition/bullwhip-effect>

¹⁸ [ISO - ISO 31000 — Risk management](#)

Figure 20 Bowtie unexpected threats and consequences¹⁹

A risk event does not include events that are caused by a stakeholder not carrying out his or her responsibilities correctly or a deliberate act of fraud.

What is risk management?

Risk management is the process of identifying, evaluating, and prioritizing risks followed by the coordinated application of resources to minimize, monitor, and control the probability or impact of unfortunate events. Risk management can also aim to grasp opportunities.

The goal of risk management is not to eliminate all risks but to understand which risks are worth taking and to mitigate those that could negatively affect an organization’s objectives.

Figure 21 Illustration of risk management process²⁰

¹⁹ Pearson, Strategy and Risk: 2 sides of one coin – Taking care of the present (polgovpro.blog), 2020

²⁰ ISO 31000 | Overview of the Leading Risk Management Standard (advisera.com)

Risk management is a highly mature field of expertise. We translated its frameworks, principles and processes into three research activities in this study: Risk identification, risk prioritization and risk mitigation (see figure 22 below):

Risk identification

- Quantify supply chain vulnerabilities
- Estimate potential delays
- Administration of *Risk ID*, *Risk description* and *Risk analysis* in risk register

Risk prioritization

- Focus on risk events with unacceptable delays

Risk mitigation

- Select typical risk mitigation strategy
- Quantify vulnerability reduction
- Estimate delay reduction
- Administration of *Residual risk analysis* in risk register

Figure 22 Risk identification, prioritization, and mitigation

And the application of these three risk management activities in this study are connected to the procurement activities and project critical paths as follows:

When addressing the causes of risks, multiple risk mitigation strategies can be included in the six procurement process steps and thereby (partially) mitigate the exposure to those risk events by reducing the probability of occurrence and/or the impact on the procurement and supply chain lead-time and the critical path of the project

A large amount of information and data needs to be systematically analyzed during the risk identification and mitigation activities. A simplified risk register (see below) is for the administration of information. The full risk registers for all three case study components are included in appendix D.

Table 7 Example setup risk register

Risk ID	Risk description			Risk analysis						Residual risk analysis			
	Effect category: (1) impact on sourcing (2) impact on value density (3) impact on routing (4) impact on flow destination (5) impact on flow volume	Impacted procurement process step: 1 - Marktverkenning 2 - Uitvraag subcontractors 3 - Subcontract selection, FID 4 - Ontwerpen en maken van component 5 - Afnemen component - FAT factory acceptance test 6 - Logistiek	Normal duration of process [months]	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVI]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	Mitigation effectiveness on LIKELIHOOD	Mitigation effectiveness on IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVI]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]
Meter	1	1	6	13%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	13%	0%	0	0
Meter	2	1	6	1%	100%	0,077682	6	0%	0%	1%	100%	0,077682	6

Note: Causes of risks and/or associated mitigation strategies that related to processes beyond the scope of procurement and the supply chain are put out of scope of this research. However, to achieve the highest quality result, risk management in supply chains should be an integral and holistic endeavor.

4.2 Risk identification

Procurement and supply chain related issues are a significant contributor to infrastructure project delays. Careful planning, effective contract management, supplier capacity assessment, and proactive risk management in the procurement process is crucial to minimize delays.

Despite all efforts done, a complete overview of risks is an unrealistic to expect, and possibly even undesirable to develop. It may be more desirable to be well prepared for a selective list of negative effects that are the *consequence* of risk events occurring. By focusing on dealing with effects, an organization can be considered more flexible and agile as this enables them to also deal with the many threats and risks that were not foreseen.

We therefore shift the focus from identifying causes of risk events to the identification of undesirable effects and consequences that any unknown risk event may lead to.

We define a set of variables that represent the infinitely long list of causes for plausible manufacturing supply chain risks and consequential delays. These variables, categorized into three levels—country level, firm level, and component level—are original contributions of this study and serve as a suggested supplement to some of the tools presented in Chapter 3. The maturity, resilience, and scalability of a component supply chain are assessed using these variables. This systematic evaluation of the supply chain sheds light on the level of risk associated with the timely supply of components from the corresponding manufacturing supply chain.

These variables are;

Country level variables

- WGI_i is the weighted World Government Index for the country in which firm i is headquartered.
- DIS_i is the weighted distance between the Netherlands (Amsterdam) and firm i 's headquarters' host country's capital.
- RES_i is a dummy which indicates whether there are EU-imposed trade restrictions for the country in which firm i is headquartered.
- $TRADE_REL_i$ denotes the intensity of existing trade relations between the Netherlands and the country in which firm i is headquartered.
- CUL_DIF_i denotes the cultural difference between the Netherlands and the country in which firm i is headquartered.
- LOG_BOT_i captures the presence of potential logistical bottlenecks (e.g. vulnerable canals or the option of piracy) on the sea route between the Netherlands
- $LOCK_i$ is a binary variable that denotes whether firm i 's headquarters' host country is landlocked or not.

Firm level variables:

- S_i is the market share of firm i in percentage points. S_i is a function of size and position of firm i .
- $SHARE_i$ is market share of firm i in percentage points divided by 100
- ESG_i is the Environmental Social Governance Index of firm i .

Component level variables

- SEA_c is a binary variable that equals 1 if the component in question needs to be transported by ship, and 0 otherwise.
- $SCAL_POT_c$ captures the scalability potential of the component, captured by its reliance and resemblance of existing industries.
- TRL_c captures the versatility (the breadth of applicability) of the component in question
- NL_DEM_c represents the Dutch demand for a component with specific performance characteristics and, if relevant, specific certification and regulation compliances.

4.2.1 Methodology for estimating the chance of delay

As discussed, the focus in the risk assessment is not directed towards the myriad potential risk events, each with varying probabilities of occurrence. Rather, focus is narrowed down to a finite set of effects or consequences stemming from these events. In our analysis we focus on five effects. These are²¹;

1. **E1 - Sourcing:** This dimension focuses on the origins of resources or materials crucial to hydrogen components within the supply chain. It encompasses factors such as the reliability of suppliers, adherence to environmental and social governance standards, geographical proximity to production facilities, and compliance with EU regulations, including sanctions. Additionally, considerations of the firm's Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance are pertinent.
2. **E2 - Flow Destination:** This aspect centers on the final destinations or end-users within the supply chain. Factors such as market demand for hydrogen-based technologies, existing trade relations, distribution channels, and adherence to EU-imposed sanctions are critical considerations. The scalability potential and versatility of the components are also relevant factors in determining their destination within the supply chain.
3. **E3 - Routing:** Routing within the hydrogen component supply chain addresses the pathways taken by goods or information. This includes considerations of transportation routes, distance, logistical channels, and potential points of congestion or disruption. Ensuring efficient and secure routing is essential for maintaining the integrity and reliability of hydrogen component deliveries.
4. **E4 - Flow Volume:** Flow volume refers to the quantity or volume of hydrogen components moving through the supply chain. Influencing factors include economies of scale in production, scalability potential of the components, and production capacities of manufacturing facilities. Managing flow volume effectively is crucial for optimizing production processes and meeting market demand for hydrogen technologies.
5. **E5 - Value Density:** This dimension examines the quality, or ability to meet the performance requirements, of hydrogen components. It also includes factors such as product differentiation and certification compliancy. Additionally, the scalability potential and versatility of the components play a significant role in determining their value density and impact on the overall supply chain.

For each effect of the hydrogen component supply chain, we develop an equation that produces an index number that captures the vulnerability of that part of the supply chain.

The 14 variables introduced in the previous section are used to describe these five effects. Each of these factors is assigned a weight based on the firm's market share—the bigger the firm's market share, the more significant the factor will be.

We use these weighted factors to calculate the index number for each aspect. The higher the number, the greater the vulnerability of that part of the supply chain. This method helps us pinpoint where the vulnerabilities are and what the effect of potential (post-)mitigation strategies are.

²¹ [MITx: Supply Chain Fundamentals | edX](#)

For each of the five effects, the estimated chance of delay is measured as follows;

E1: Sourcing

$$F(S, SHARE, WGI, NL_DEM, ESG, CUL_DIF) = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha SHARE_i + \eta(1 - WGI_i) + \nu(1 - NL_DEM_c) + \beta(1 - ESG_i) + \tau CUL_DIF_i)$$

E2: Flow Destination

$$F(S, SHARE, TRADE_REL) = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha SHARE_i + \gamma(1 - TRADE_REL_i))$$

E3: Routing

$$F(S, SHARE, TRADE_REL, SEA, DIS, LOG_BOT, LOCKED) = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha SHARE_i + \gamma(1 - TRADE_REL_i) + SEA_c(\theta DIS_i + \delta LOG_BOT_i)(1 - SEA_c LOCKED_i))$$

E4: Flow Volume

$$F(S, SHARE, NL_DEM) = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha SHARE_i + \nu(1 - NL_DEM_c))$$

E5: Value Density

$$F(S, SHARE, ESG, SCAL_POT, TRL, CE) = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha SHARE_i + \beta(1 - ESG_i) + \varepsilon(1 - SCAL_POT_c) + \vartheta(1 - TRL_c) + \mu(1 - CE_c))$$

Further, $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \varepsilon, \theta, \vartheta, \eta, \tau, \nu$ and μ are parameters.

For the estimated chance of delay equations, E1-E5, we create an index by dividing the aforementioned formulas by the maximum of that specific formula.

E.g. for Sourcing the index will be calculated as follow;

$$SCV_{INDEX} = \frac{F(S, SHARE, WGI, NL_DEM, ESG, CUL_DIF)}{\max \{F(S, SHARE, WGI, NL_DEM, ESG, CUL_DIF)\}}$$

Note that in the bottom line of the aforementioned equation the maximum would be given by a (potentially fictional) monopolistic firm with little to no regard to its ESG in a faraway country associated with a low WGI. Hence for the maximum S_i is equal to 100 located in the country with the worst possible WGI, CUL_DIF and ESG combination.

The parameter values provided play a critical role in quantifying the various risks and vulnerabilities within the supply chain for hydrogen components. A comprehensive overview of each variable is presented in the appendix.

The parameter values were carefully established and validated by experts in procurement, supply chain management, and infrastructure projects. These experts used their experience to assign accurate weights to each variable, ensuring the analysis reflects real-world conditions, including factors like market share, governance quality, and logistical risks.

The parameter values are as follows;

Table 8 Parameter values

Variables	Parameter values
SHARE	0,5
ESG	0
WGI	1
DIS	0
RES	1
TRADE REL	0
CUL DIF	0
LOG BOT	0,5
LOCK	1
SEA	1
SCAL POT	1
TRL	1
CE MARK	0
NL DEM	0,2

Notice that some parameters are set to zero because experts deemed them irrelevant for the current analysis. However, we retained them in the methodology to ensure thoroughness and allow for future adjustments if needed.

The Supply Chain Vulnerability Index per effect category is used in the risk register and is representing the ‘likelihood’ of that risk effect firing. When fired, the total delay per relevant procurement process still needs to be estimated. This estimation is discussed in the next section.

4.2.2 Matching effect categories to procurement process steps

In this section, we align the effect categories with the different procurement process steps to understand how disturbances in these categories impact the potential delay.

The impact on planning (delay) arises when a disturbance occurs in one of the effect categories, affecting the procurement steps. This impact is measured as a percentage of the normal estimated time for each procurement step. Some effect categories are unrelated to specific procurement steps, while others have a partial impact. In these cases, if a disturbance occurs, it results in a partial delay in certain procurement steps. Other effect categories can have a full impact, meaning that if a disturbance occurs, the estimated time for the affected procurement steps will double, leading to a 100% delay.

The effects are summarized in the matrix below;

Table 9 Matching procurement process steps to effect categories

Effect categories

		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5
Procurement process steps	Market survey	0%	100%	0%	100%	100%
	Invitation to tender	0%	100%	0%	100%	100%
	FID	0%	0%	0%	50%	50%
	Design & produce	100%	100%	0%	0%	100%
	FAT	0%	10%	0%	0%	0%
	Logistics	100%	0%	100%	0%	0%

4.2.3 Methodology for estimating the potential delay and calculating the effects of mitigating measures

For a critical path analysis we want to calculate for each process step:

- the maximum potential delay;
- the expected delay;
- the probability distribution for the delay.

Furthermore, we want to perform these calculations both for the base case, i.e. *without* mitigating measures, and for scenarios *with* mitigating measures. Calculating the above results enables us to support the decision making process by comparing various scenarios in terms of costs (extra budget required for the mitigating measures) and benefits (reducing potential delays). Which (combination) of the three indicators above is used in the decision making process is a matter of preference and depends on the further use of the indicator and the risk appetite of the organization.

We will calculate the indicators in the order above.

Maximum potential delay

The maximum potential delay, per procurement step and per effect category, is calculated as follows;

$$\text{Max delay} = \text{Normal duration of procurement step} * \text{Impact on planning, in \%}$$

The impacts on planning, measured in percentages, are presented in the matrix-table in section 4.2.2. The normal duration of the procurement process steps for each component are;

Table 10 Estimated normal duration of the procurement steps for each component

Normal Duration	Market survey	Invitation to tender	FID	Design & produce	FAT	Logistics
Hydrogen Burners	6	12	2	18	3	6
Hydrogen Compressors	6	12	2	24	3	6
Flow Meters	6	12	2	12	3	6

Multiplying these two tables yields the following results for the maximum potential delays for hydrogen burners:

Table 11 Maximum delay for hydrogen burners

Maximum delay for hydrogen burners		Effect category					Total
		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	
Procurement process steps	Market survey	0	6	0	6	6	18
	Invitation to tender	0	12	0	12	12	36
	FID	0	0	0	1	1	2
	Design & produce	18	18	0	0	18	54
	FAT	0	0,3	0	0	0	0,3
	Logistics	6	0	6	0	0	12
	Total	24	36,3	6	19	37	122,3

Note that we assume that the effect categories are independent, which implies that all delays may be added up to yield the total potential delay for a specific procurement process step.

The next step is calculating the expected delay. The expected delay is the product of the likelihood of delay (as estimated by the equations for each effect category, presented in section 4.2.1.) and the maximum delay.

$$\text{Expected delay} = \text{Likelihood of delay} * \text{Max delay}$$

For the hydrogen burners this yields the following table:

Table 12 Estimated maximum delay for hydrogen burners

Estimated maximum delay for hydrogen burners		Effect category					Total
		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	
	Likelihood	23%	8%	11%	33%	58%	
Procurement process steps	Market survey	0	0,48	0	2,00	3,46	5,94
	Invitation to tender	0	0,95	0	4,01	6,93	11,89
	FID	0	0	0	0,33	0,58	0,91
	Design & produce	4,05	1,43	0	0	10,39	15,87
	FAT	0	0,02	0	0	0	0,02
	Logistics	1,35	0	0,66	0	0	2,01
	Total	5,40	2,88	0,66	6,34	21,35	36,64

Probability distribution for the delay

Finally, we can determine the probability distribution for the delay using Monte Carlo simulation (explained in paragraph 4.5.3. For all likelihoods a uniform distribution between 0 and the estimated likelihood is used, and the result for hydrogen burners is shown in the figure below:

Figure 23 Monte Carlo simulation of the probability distribution for the delay

As an illustration, the P85 is indicated in the figure, which could be used as an indicator to compare scenarios. In this case, there is an 85% probability that the total delay is less than 58,2 months.

Calculating the effects of mitigating measures

The total effect of a mitigating measure on the potential delay is calculated both on the likelihood (how much the likelihood of a delay change after the mitigating measure is implemented) and on the impact (how much does the delay, if it occurs, change).

The change in likelihood is calculated by estimating new values for the parameters used to calculate the SCVI, yielding an adjusted value for the SCVI. See paragraph 4.4 for more detail on this calculation.

The change in impact is calculated by estimating the reduction in the original impact that is achieved by implementing a mitigating measure. The table below shows the estimates used in our example of the hydrogen burners for the first three mitigating measures. The reduction is assumed to be the same for all effect categories.

Table 13 Effect of mitigation measures on procurement steps, in percentages

Mitigation measure	Market survey	Invitation to tender	FI D	Design & produce	FA T	Logistics
Conduct due diligence (market/technology/implementation)	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Allocate risks to appropriate party	0%	0%	0%	25%	25%	25%
Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts	0%	0%	0%	50%	50%	50%
...	...	...	...	...	...	...

The interpretation of this table is that conducting due diligence, in each step of the procurement process, would yield a reduction of 25% of the potential delay. Note that performing due diligence in all steps implies taking six mitigating measures. For the second measure, the assessment is that there is no potential benefit for the first three process steps, and a 25% reduction for each of the final three.

The subsequent calculation of the residual risk, i.e. the risk that remains after the implementation of mitigating measures, is conducted identically to the base case.

Note, the full list of data for the intermediary steps is given in the Risk Register presented in Appendix D.

4.2.4 Risk identification results in graphics

For each effect we have two sets of variables. One, the chance of delay, and two, the optional maximum delay measured in months. The latter is the potential maximum impact on the timeline. Together, the chance of delay and the potential delay forms the supply chain risk. In the pyramid below we have plotted this risk. For each graph, the horizontal axes denotes the chance of delay from low to high, and the vertical axes denotes the potential maximum delay.

The lower row of graphs in the pyramid presents the unique estimated risk for each individual effect, while the graph at the top provides an average of those effects in one consolidated view.

In the graphs, the green area represents the risk-free zone, indicating minimal impact, regardless of the likelihood of delay, or a very low probability of delay, or both. The yellow area signifies moderate risk, while the red area highlights unacceptable risks that require immediate attention.

For the component Flow Meters, few concerns arise. Only the effect related to Value Density is positioned in the unacceptable risk zone. On the other hand, Hydrogen Burners and Compressors show more areas of concern, particularly in the effect categories of Flow Destination and Value Density, where both are located in the unacceptable risk zone. This suggests that the purchaser of those components may face supply chain related challenges to acquire that specific component. Additionally, in the effect category Sourcing, both components fall within the moderate risk zone.

Overall, Routing and Flow Volume do not appear to pose significant issues for any of the components.

When reviewing the top graph, which averages the five effect categories, we observe that the supply chain for Flow Meters presents no serious risk. However, Hydrogen Burners and Compressors show moderate risk, with Hydrogen Compressors presenting the highest level of risk.

Figure 24 Supply chain risk pyramid

4.3 Risk prioritization

A prioritization step is needed to focus the mitigation strategies and efforts on the unacceptable consequences only. Acceptable risks can receive mitigation attention only after unacceptable risks are mitigated (or accepted nonetheless). Note that a risk may be acceptable at first, but transform into an unacceptable risk any time which stresses the importance of continuous iteration of the risk identification step.

The matrix-based visualization of risk events is used to prioritize the risks that require immediate mitigation (see below). We assume that any delay that impacts the critical path of the project planning is judged *unacceptable*. And risks that threaten the critical path but are not (yet) delaying it require risk mitigation strategies that reduce the risk score only when the likelihood, or supply chain vulnerability, is high. The risks with a low impact and low likelihood are considered acceptable and positioned in the lower left corner of the graph. In practice, these boundaries are more fuzzy as we will see in the subsequent sections.

Figure 25 Risk prioritization: risks with unacceptable consequences need to be eliminated

Applying this prioritization approach to our hydrogen infrastructure component supply chains we find that risk mitigation strategies are required to reduce delays originating from Flow Destination and Value Density effects for all three components. From our case studies:

Figure 26 Supply chain risk pyramid

4.4 Risk mitigation

An organization may be able to reduce the risk score through actions or decisions that reduce the likelihood and/or the effect. Those actions or decisions are referred to as risk mitigation strategies. The effectiveness of mitigation strategies depends strongly on the risk and the strategy. The figure below shows a very effective strategy applied to risk 2, and an ineffective strategy applied to risk 6.

After briefly introduces risk mitigation background information, this paragraph discusses the hydrogen component supply chain risk mitigation strategies found in this study.

Figure 27 An example of 9 risks in a risk matrix including a selection risks received mitigation actions with low (risk 2, 4) to high (risk 2, 8) effectiveness

A set of four types of strategies provide a simple framework for an organization to mitigate risks, allowing them to choose the most appropriate approach based on the nature of the risk and their specific circumstances. These four classical strategy types are:

- **Avoid** the possibility of the risk occurring through actions or decisions that completely eliminate the specific risk. An example: not using a cargo ship for transport eliminates the risk of harbor bottleneck delays.
- **Reduce** the possibility of occurrence by preventive mitigation measures and/or deploy responsive measures to deal with the consequences when they unfold. An example: Leave the intellectual property of system designs at the OEM reduces the likelihood of having disputes and IP issues between supplier and purchaser.
- **Transfer** potential consequences of a risk to stakeholder(s) able and willing to take the responsibility. Partial transfer may also be a viable strategy. An example: Develop an infrastructure project together with a partner can imply sharing the consequences of risks with that partner.
- **Accept** the presence of the risk and deal with the consequences when the risk fires. This strategy is usually chosen when the effort or cost of other strategies outweighs the potential risk reducing effect. An example: Cyber-attack on a global scale disrupting communication between supplier and purchaser.

The risk mitigation strategies compiled in this study are categorized based on these four types. See the table below for the introduction and elaboration on the mitigation strategies found.

Table 14 Mitigation strategies categorized

#	Mitigation type	Mitigation strategy	Mechanism or incentive
1	Reduce	Two-stage procurement process	agility
2	Accept, Reduce	Build in margins	agility
3	Reduce	Adjust project, goals, scope and specs	agility
4	Reduce	Procurement organization aligned to corporate organization with next-generation capabilities	agility
5	Reduce	Leverage intellectual property as collateral	carrot
6	Avoid, Transfer, Reduce	Pool order of component purchase with partner procurers to increase order size	carrot
7	Reduce	Allocate risks to appropriate party	collaborate
8	Reduce	Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts	collaborate
9	Reduce	Enhance procurement transparency	collaborate
10	Reduce	Outsourcing component parts	collaborate
11	Reduce	Develop strong relationships with suppliers	collaborate
12	Avoid, Reduce	Establish long-term supply contracts	collaborate
13	Avoid, Reduce	Use existing trustworthy relationships	collaborate
14	Reduce, avoid	Develop / select alternative technology type	hedge
15	Reduce	Build in redundancy by purchasing two different types of systems	hedge
16	Reduce	Build in redundancy by purchasing one component type from two or more different suppliers	hedge
17	Reduce, avoid	Develop national supply on component assembly level	hedge
18	Reduce	Develop stockpiles of component	hedge
19	Reduce	Establish conflict of interest policies and mechanisms	stick
20	Reduce	High(er) frequency of audits and control (by an external auditor)	stick
21	Reduce	Demand specific experience or track record	stick
22	Reduce, avoid	Conduct due diligence (e.g. market, technology, financial, implementation)	study
23	Reduce	Develop in-house technical expertise	study
24	Reduce	Use technology readiness assessments	study
25	Reduce	Testing, prototyping, simulations	study

Many more mitigation strategies exist that can effectively reduce supply chain risks. Most of those strategies make use of one of six mechanisms or incentives that are summarized below. Scanning these mechanisms or incentives can help the brainstorming process for more mitigation strategies.

Table 15 Mitigation strategies' mechanisms or incentives specified

Mechanism or incentive	Definition/description of the mechanism or incentive
Hedge	A mechanism to reduce or offset potential negative effects. In supply chains, hedging often involves using financial instruments or diversifying suppliers to protect against risks.
agility	The ability of supply chain stakeholders (individually and/or collectively) to respond quickly and effectively to unexpected changes or disruptions. An agile supply chain can rapidly adapt to market shifts, demand fluctuations, or supply issues.
Carrot	A positive incentive used to encourage desired behaviour or actions from supply chain partners. This can include financial rewards, preferential treatment, or other benefits for meeting certain performance targets.
stick	A negative incentive used to discourage undesirable behaviour of supply chain stakeholders. This might involve fines, reduced orders, or termination of contracts when agreed-upon performance targets are not met.
study	The process of analysing and understanding supply chain designs and dynamics and the associated risks, their potential impacts, and effective mitigation strategies. This involves gathering data, conducting research, and evaluating different scenarios to improve the ongoing management of risks.
collaborate	Working together with supply chain partners by sharing information, resources, and risks. Collaboration often involves joint planning, transparent communication, and coordinated responses to potential disruptions in the supply chain.

4.4.1 Methodology for estimating the effect of mitigation strategies on the chance of delay

In this section, we outline the approach used to estimate how mitigation strategies influence the likelihood of delays in the project.

It is important to note that the mitigation strategies do not directly affect the chance of delay itself. Instead, they influence variables that impact the likelihood of delay. These adjustments were factored into the matrix through the relevant parameters.

The formulas E1-E5 (as given in chapter 4.2.1) adjusted for relevant mitigation strategies (M_v) are as follows;

E1: Sourcing

$$F_{sourcing} = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha M_{share} SHARE_i + \eta M_{WGI} (1 - WGI_i) + \beta M_{ESG} (1 - ESG_i) + \tau M_{CULDIF} CUL_DIF_i)$$

E2: Flow Destination

$$F_{flow\ destination} = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha M_{share} SHARE_i + \gamma M_{trade_rel} (1 - TRADE_REL_i))$$

E3: Routing

$$F_{routing} = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha M_{share} SHARE_i + \gamma M_{trade_rel} (1 - TRADE_REL_i) + SEA_c (\theta DIS_i + \delta M_{log_bot} LOG_BOT_i)) (1 - SEA_c LOCKED_i)$$

E4: Flow Volume

$$F_{flow\ volume} = \sum_{i=0}^n \alpha M_{share} S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} SHARE_i$$

E5: Value Density

$$F_{value\ density} = \sum_{i=0}^n S_i^{\frac{3}{2}} (\alpha M_{share} SHARE_i + \beta M_{ESG} (1 - ESG_i) + \varepsilon M_{scal_pot} (1 - SCAL_POT_c) + \vartheta M_{TRL} (1 - TRL_c) + \mu M_{CE} (1 - CE_c))$$

Where;

$$M_{var} = \prod_{m=1}^n m_{var,m}^{M_m}$$

Where M_m equals 1 if mitigation strategy m is implemented and equals 0 if mitigation strategy m is not implanted.

Further, $m_{var,m}^{M_m}$ is the specific parameter of variable v associated with mitigation strategy m .

The index will be calculated similarly as explained in section 4.2.1. For simplicity, a standardized approach has been applied across the board, assigning either no effect (0) or a partial effect (0.5) to each mitigation strategy. This ensures a uniform evaluation process and allows for a clearer understanding of how the mitigation actions influence the risks of delays. Below is a table showing which mitigation strategies affect specific variables.

Table 16 Parameter effect of mitigation strategies

Mitigation strategy	S	ESG	WGI	DIS	RES	TRADE REL	CUL DIF	LOG BOT	LOCK	SEA	SCAL POT	TRL	CE MARK	NLDEM
Conduct due diligence (market/technology/implementation)		0,5	0,5		0,5	0,5	0,5		0,5					
<u>Allocate risks to appropriate party</u>								0,5		0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	
<u>Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts</u>	0,5	0,5	0,5											
two-stage procurement process	0,5					0,5	0,5			0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	
Develop in-house technical expertise											0,5	0,5	0,5	
Use technology readiness assessments														
<u>Leverage intellectual property as collateral</u>	0,5										0,5	0,5	0,5	
0,5											0,5	0,5		
Establish conflict of interest policies and mechanisms		0,5	0,5				0,5						0,5	
<u>Enhance procurement transparency</u>														0,5
<u>Build in margins</u>				0,5				0,5			0,5		0,5	
<u>Adjust project, goals, scope and specs</u>	0,5				0,5						0,5	0,5		
Develop / select alternative technology type	0,5								0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	
Testing, prototyping, simulations	0,5													
<u>Outsourcing component parts</u>											0,5		0,5	
Build in redundancy by purchasing two different types of systems	0,5			0,5				0,5				0,5	0,5	
Build in redundancy by purchasing one component type from two or more different suppliers				0,5				0,5				0,5	0,5	
<u>Pool order of component purchase with partner procurers to increase order size</u>											0,5		0,5	0,5
Checking suppliers more frequently (do it yourself / have an external auditor do it)		0,5	0,5										0,5	
Requiring specific experience														
0,5											0,5	0,5	0,5	
Develop national supply on component assembly level	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5	0,5				
Develop stockpiles of component				0,5				0,5						
<u>Establish long-term supply contracts</u>	0,5	0,5												0,5
<u>Use existing trustworthy relationships</u>	0,5	0,5	0,5				0,5							0,5

4.4.2 Estimating the effect of mitigation strategies on the delay

If implemented, each mitigation strategy may also influence the six procurement steps, potentially reducing the estimated delay.

We chose between an effect of 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, or 100%, where 0% indicates no impact of the mitigation strategy on the specific procurement step, and 100% represents the full impact of the strategy on that step.

The table below outlines the extent of delay reduction for each strategy, based on expert assessments. The matrix table is structured as follows: vertically, all the mitigation strategies are listed, while horizontally, the six procurement steps are displayed.

Table 17 Effect of mitigation strategies on procurement steps, in percentages

Mitigation Strategy	Market Exploration	Tendering	FID	Design/ Construction	FAT	Logistics
Conduct due diligence (market/technology/implementation)	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Allocate risks to appropriate party	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Two-stage procurement process	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Develop in-house technical expertise	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Use technology readiness assessments	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Enhance procurement transparency	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Build in margins	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Adjust project, goals, scope, and specs	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Develop/select alternative technology type	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Testing, prototyping, simulations	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Build in redundancy by purchasing two different types of systems	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Build in redundancy by purchasing one component type from two or more suppliers	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Pool order of component purchase with partner procurers to increase order size	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
More frequent supplier audits (internal/external auditors)	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Require specific experience	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Develop strong relationships with suppliers	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Procurement organization aligned with corporate organization	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%
Develop national supply on component assembly level	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Develop stockpiles of components	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Establish long-term supply contracts	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%
Use existing trustworthy relationships	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%	25%

4.4.3 Estimated effect of mitigation on supply chain risk

This section presents a visual representation of how mitigation strategies influence supply chain risk, with both the cumulative impact across procurement steps and the probability of delay considered. The graphs provide a clear depiction of how each mitigation strategy affects overall risk, illustrating the varying degrees of effectiveness in reducing both the likelihood and the impact of delays.

The graphs are structured as follows, the vertical axis represents the cumulative impact across the procurement steps (measured in months of delay), and the horizontal axis shows the probability of delay for each supply chain effect (E1-E5). Each graph corresponds to one of the five supply chain effects.

The red dot marks the starting point, where no mitigation strategies have been applied. The blue dots illustrate the effects of individual mitigation strategies. Some strategies have a limited effect, impacting mildly the delay in the procurement stages (vertical axis) or the probability of delay (horizontal axis). Other strategies show a stronger impact on either or both axes, shifting the position from the red dot towards the lower left corner, which represents the "risk-free" zone.

It is important to note that each mitigation strategy is applied separately because they may not be independent of each other. In other words, the effect of one mitigation strategy could be different when another strategy is in place, potentially altering the overall outcome. This approach ensures that we accurately capture the individual impact of each strategy.

Effect of Mitigation strategies – Hydrogen Compressors

Figure 28 Effect of mitigation strategies on various supply chain risk effects, hydrogen compressors

Effect of Mitigation strategies – Hydrogen Compressors

Figure 29 Effect of mitigation strategies on various supply chain risk effects, hydrogen compressors, effective measures highlighted

In previous graphs, the strategies that are most effective in reducing both the cumulative procurement delay and the chance of delay are encircled to highlight their significance.

If the red dot is already in the risk-free zone, no circle is drawn, regardless of the effectiveness of the strategies.

For certain components, we observe that a specific set of mitigation strategies consistently proves to be highly successful, regardless of the component in question. For each chance-of-delay effect, we list the most effective mitigation strategies, highlighting both those that significantly reduce risk and those that minimize impact. These are listed below;

Table 18 overview effective mitigation strategies

Effective mitigation strategies

E1 sourcing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts. - Conduct due-diligence - Establish long-term supplier contract - Testing, prototyping and simulation - Adjust projects goals, scope, and specs - Pool order of component purchase with partner-procurers to increase order size
E2 Flow destination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share risks and profits through collaborative contracts. - Conduct due-diligence - Testing, prototyping and simulation - Adjust projects goals, scope, and specs
E3 Routing	Irrelevant (all starting points are in the risk-free zone)
E4 Flow volume	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use existing trustworthy relationships - Pool order of component purchase with partner-procurers to increase order size - Establish long-term supplier contract
E5 Value density	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Testing, prototyping and simulation - Adjust projects goals, scope, and specs - Develop in-house technical expertise

4.5 Translating risk management insights into project planning

In paragraph 3.3.1 the a base case for the procurement process planning was established. This paragraph shows how risks can be added to the base case and how this can be used in analyses.

4.5.1 Adding risks to the base case

As a next step in the process, findings from the risk register are added to the base case planning, focusing on examining potential delays during component procurement. This involves determining for each procurement step what the probability of a delay is, and the duration of the delay should it occur. The result of this exercise is shown in the two figures below. The upper figure shows the expected delays, i.e. taking the probabilities of the delays into account. The lower figure shows the maximum delays, i.e. assuming that all delays actually occur.

Figure 30: Expected and maximum timelines for the base case taking into account the risks identified, but without implementing mitigating measures

The methodology behind the calculation of the risks is explained in paragraph 4.2.

4.5.2 Applying mitigating measures in a scenario

In the third step, a set of mitigating measures is applied to the base case, resulting in a scenario with reduced risk of delays. To this extent, for 25 mitigating measures their effects on the possible delay in each procurement process step was determined. By subsequently selecting any number of mitigating measures to implement the residual risk for the planning can be calculated, as is shown in the figures below. Again, the upper figure shows the expected delays, i.e. taking the probabilities of the delays into account, the lower figure shows the maximum delays, i.e. assuming that all delays actually occur.

Figure 31: Expected and maximum timelines for the base case taking into account the risks identified, and implementing mitigating measures

The methodology behind the calculation of the risks is explained in paragraph 4.4.

4.5.3 Applying Monte Carlo simulation in risk analysis

Additional insight into project risks may be gained by applying Monte Carlo simulation to the risk model. In a Monte Carlo simulation, a number of iterations is run where in each iteration a random sample is drawn from each parameter distribution and the subsequent delay is calculated. These results per iteration are then combined in a histogram to produce a probability distribution for the delay, which may look like the figure below.

Figure 32: Probability distribution (example) of the total delay resulting from Monte Carlo simulation

The distribution above can be used to determine indicators such as the probability that no delay will occur, or (shown in Figure 32) the maximum delay that will occur with a probability of 85% ('P85'). Such indicators can then be used to determine policy or the size of a risk reservation in the budget. Furthermore, they may be used in the decision process whether or not to implement certain mitigating measures as shown in the figure below where the resulting distribution is shown after a set of mitigating measures is implemented.

Figure 33: Probability distribution (example) of the total delay after implementation of mitigating measures

Figure 33 would indicate that the selected set of mitigating measures would result in an increase of the probability that no delay will occur from 9.7% to 36.0%, and a decrease in the P85 from 24.9 to 10.6 months.

5 Scenario analysis

This chapter aims to provide insight into how various future conditions and uncertainties may affect the development and rollout of hydrogen infrastructure. By modeling different scenarios, we can better understand how changes in factors such as technological advancements, policy frameworks, market shifts, and fluctuations in supply and demand influence project timelines, costs, and risks.

Scenario analysis serves as a framework that prepares us for a range of future scenarios and offers valuable insights into the key risks and opportunities. This enables project leaders and policymakers to make more informed decisions by mapping out the potential effects of different circumstances on infrastructure planning and the supply chain, allowing them to better anticipate future challenges and uncertainties.

As technologies evolve and markets shift, the weights and parameters underlying our scenarios also change. These developments can lead to new scenarios that take into account changing conditions, such as technological progress, supplier availability, or adjustments in policy and market conditions. This dynamic process helps continuously adjust and evaluate strategies, which is essential for effectively responding to future developments.

Through these scenarios, it becomes clear how variations in technological development and market conditions impact the risks, costs, and timelines of hydrogen infrastructure projects. Continuously adjusting and evaluating these scenarios is crucial to effectively anticipating potential future challenges and ensuring the resilience of projects.

We explore three scenarios: The supply chain risk increase in case of a lower technological readiness level (TRL) of a component (5.1), the impact on supply chain risks when the number of suppliers turns out to be lower than expected (5.2) and the effect of taking multiple complementing risk mitigation strategies to lower the risk score (5.3).

5.1 Scenario: Impact of Changes in TRL Levels of Specific Components

In this scenario analysis, we explore how variations in Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) affect the likelihood of delays in hydrogen infrastructure projects. TRL is a key indicator of a component's maturity, and changes in its level can significantly influence project timelines and risks. By analysing scenarios where TRL increases or decreases for specific components, we gain insights into how these fluctuations impact the probability of delays and the broader implications for project planning and risk management.

5.1.1 Higher TRL for Hydrogen Burners

In this example, we explore the impact of an increase in the Technology Readiness Level (TRL) for hydrogen burners, which often occurs as technology advances over time. We assume that the TRL index for hydrogen burners increases from 0.72 to 0.9. This scenario is depicted in the figures below, with the base case on the left and the improved case on the right.

The results indicate that such an advancement in TRL significantly reduces the likelihood of delays in project timelines. Specifically, the probability of delay decreases from moderately high to low. It is important to note that this analysis focuses solely on the effect of TRL changes on product quality, as this is the area most directly influenced by improvements in technology readiness.

Figure 34 Scenario of higher TRL for hydrogen burners, for Value Density

5.1.2 Lower TRL for Hydrogen Compressors

In contrast, we examine the potential consequences of a decrease in TRL for hydrogen compressors. This scenario serves as a proxy for situations in which offshore hydrogen compressors, still in the early stages of development, are compared to their more mature onshore counterparts. Although the compression process remains fundamentally the same, the lower TRL of offshore compressors can be attributed to the challenges associated with their operational environment. Offshore compressors are exposed to more aggressive conditions and are more difficult to service than their onshore equivalents, which places additional demands on the supply chain to ensure reliability and maintenance. These environmental and logistical factors, rather than the compression technology itself, contribute to the lower TRL of offshore hydrogen compressors despite similarities in upstream and downstream supply chains. Here, we reduce the TRL from 0.75 to 0.375.

As expected, this decrease in TRL correlates with an increased likelihood of delays. The probability of delay rises from approximately 0.48 to 0.55. This outcome highlights the challenges associated with deploying less mature technologies in critical infrastructure projects.

Figure 35 Scenario of lower TRL for hydrogen compressors, for Value Density

These examples illustrate two important lessons:

1. Accurately Estimating TRL is Critical: The TRL of a component plays a crucial role in determining the likelihood of delays in project execution. Accurate estimation of TRL is essential for effective risk management and timeline planning.
2. The Dynamic Nature of TRL: As the TRL of a product evolves, so too will its impact on the probability of delays. Continuous monitoring of TRL progress is necessary to adjust risk assessments and project expectations accordingly.

5.2 Scenario: Impact of reduction of number of suppliers.

A reduction in the number of suppliers is a plausible outcome across various scenarios, driven by factors such as mergers and acquisitions, bankruptcies, or trade restrictions. In this scenario, we analyze the effects of focusing solely on suppliers based within the EU.

Multiple lessons were learned from the reduction of supplier numbers:

- Significant Impact on Likelihood of Delay: Limiting the supply chain to EU-based suppliers has a notable impact on the likelihood of delays across all components.
- As expected, routing does not present significant challenges since within the EU, the remaining suppliers are relatively close to each other. Proximity reduces the complexity and risks typically associated with long-distance transportation and cross-border logistics, leading to more streamlined delivery schedules.
- Hydrogen Meters Show Resilience: While we observe some changes in the likelihood of delays for hydrogen meters, the impact is not significant. This suggests that a sufficient number of EU-based producers exist for these components, mitigating the risk of supply shortages.
- Drastic Increases for Compressors and Burners: The most severe increase in delay likelihood is seen for hydrogen compressors and burners. These components are not widely produced within the EU, which could pose a future risk. As global demand for these technologies rises, non-EU countries like the US may prioritize their domestic markets over European demand, exacerbating supply challenges for the EU.

Figure 36 Supply chain risk pyramid, based on EU suppliers only

5.3 Scenario: Combination of multiple mitigation strategies

If the implemented mitigation strategies are independent from each other and have no direct relationship or interaction between them —this is to say that changes due to one mitigation strategy do not impact changes caused by the other—we can analyse the compounded effect of multiple strategies.

For this example, we analyze the effect of two different mitigation strategies on the Value Density effect of Hydrogen Burners. These strategies are;

- Develop in-house technical expertise
- Testing, prototyping, simulations

Figure 37 Compounded effect of two mitigation strategies

The results show a significant reduction in risk: The combination of independent mitigation strategies—developing in-house technical expertise and implementing testing, prototyping, and simulations—demonstrates a significant positive effect. As seen in the graph, the compounded effect of these strategies drastically reduces the maximum delay for hydrogen burners. This indicates that the two strategies work together effectively to reduce potential delays.

Since the two strategies do not interact or interfere with one another, their independent implementation allows for an additive effect. The combined approach effectively addresses different aspects of the supply chain risks and technical challenges, leading to an optimized outcome that wouldn't have been achieved by relying on a single mitigation measure alone.

This scenario highlights the importance of implementing multiple, targeted interventions. Focusing on both technical capabilities (through in-house expertise) and rigorous validation processes (through testing and simulations) provides a comprehensive mitigation strategy that strengthens both the human and technological aspects of production.

6 Discussion of the SCRM approach

6.1 Discussion of method and typical project insights

This paragraph discusses the added value and limitations of the presented research on component supply chain risks impacting the construction of hydrogen projects in general, and public infrastructure specifically in the Netherlands. It also addresses aspects that were not included in the study and suggests further developments for the supply chain risk management method.

6.1.1 The relevance of the presented results

A key value of this research lies in its methodological approach, which provides structured insights into supply chain risks. It emphasizes the necessity for an integrated approach across disciplines, such as procurement, strategy, risk management, and project organization. While many of such topics can be considered business as usual in construction projects, this interdisciplinary alignment becomes (even more) critical when dealing with non-standard projects like the construction of public hydrogen infrastructure. The likelihood of such projects going over budget and/or with delays and/or not delivering the envisioned benefits can be linked to Flyvbjerg's theory on megaproject management. In this applied research project we set out to combine state-of-the-art theory and tools with a hands-on project execution level of supply chain and procurement risk management.

However, while the method presented offers valuable insights into specific components (e.g., hydrogen gas compression systems), it does not provide a comprehensive evaluation of the entire hydrogen supply chain or all hydrogen transport network components. This study focuses on the development of a generically applicable method and we have included examples of components and project timelines to be able to apply the method. Therefore, the reader should not expect a full assessment of whether the entire hydrogen component supply chain is resilient or ready for large-scale implementation.

6.1.2 General applicability and limitations of the method

The research thus offers a structured way to assess risks by linking potential supply chain disruptions to project scheduling. This connection highlights risks tied to project timeline delays, which are crucial to mitigate in the early stages of the Dutch infrastructure development. However, the risks addressed are more relative than absolute, as is typical when performing risk assessments: the extent to which a risk event is perceived acceptable or not acceptable depends on the value judgement of the risk 'owner'. Therefore, all judgements, relative weights between criteria and the prioritization between risks being acceptable or not acceptable should be evaluated individually by the reader of this study before drawing conclusions on the outcomes based on the judgements of the researchers.

The static approach benefits from periodical updates

A limitation of the current approach is its static nature. The research presents a snapshot of supply chain risks based on current supply chain maturity and the current status of the technological readiness but does not account for future developments and changes in risk perceptions. To enhance its applicability, the method should be updated periodically to reflect changes in the external environment, such as technological advancements or shifts in market conditions. This ties into the brief demonstration of scenario 1 (section 5.1), where changes in technology readiness levels (TRL) could significantly influence risk perceptions.

A focus on components only excludes the supply of 'services'

Moreover, while this method provides a structured framework for expert opinions, it primarily focuses on component deliveries rather than service-related risks. The analysis is limited to tangible supply chain components, using them as test cases. Future studies could expand this scope to include service delivery such as engineering and construction capabilities of EPC contractors, offering a more comprehensive risk assessment. The generic design of the framework is expected to accommodate this expansion well.

Increasing depth of the method regarding the manufacturing lead-times beyond tier-1 (the OEM of the component purchased) would add major insights in underlying risks beyond the initial scope of control of the project executives. This depth was, in this first version of the method, excluded.

Relative supply chain vulnerability index scores requires large datasets

The third generic discussion point is the relative nature of the supply chain vulnerability index (SCVI) scores. The method's validity is tied to the comparison of various components and their expert verification. As the number of components analyzed increases, the reliability of this risk assessment method improves (e.g. in a point cloud of 30 component SCVIs, a 31st outlier would clearly show the higher risk of that components supply chain). This highlights the need to build and continuously refine a database of components analyzed.

6.1.3 Discussion points on specific methodology steps and topics

1. Assessing the number of components required over time is essential

The chosen level of detail in the analysis is essential. Breaking down the supply chain to a detailed component level allows for a more granular assessment of vulnerabilities. The minimum level of detail required is the level at which systems can be purchased from OEMs. Note that evaluating risks at such a system level, where components are already assembled, can hide critical vulnerabilities in the tier 2 level of that OEMs supply chain.

An infrastructure project requires many components to be assembled. Ideally, the supply chain risk assessments focusses only on those components that are expected to have a vulnerable supply chain. Identifying that 1% of critical components is challenging beforehand. This study did not cover the pre-selection of such a subset of components. Another notable omission in this research is the offshore hydrogen infrastructure component supply chain, which may play a crucial role in the future hydrogen network in the Netherlands.

2. Supply chain OEM characteristics can be expanded upon

Two topics are explicitly worth noting regarding the TRL assessment during the risk identification:

- The technical maturity of components includes the compliancy to certification requirements. For instance, components that have not yet received certification from a national measurement institute are indicated as a lower TRL, ultimately translating in a higher supply chain vulnerability score. It may be worthwhile to split TRL and certification compliancy in this method to address both topics in a transparent fashion.
- No difference is assumed between technologies at maximum TRL (9 out of 9) that currently have small production scales, versus large-scale automated production. One may argue that

components, and their manufacturing supply chain of OEMs, that are TRL 9 at low production volumes may not maintain that same level of technological readiness at high volumes.

3. Supply Chain Risk identification and Prioritization requires data and value judgement

High quality data and information collection is a key challenge in this method. Our approach incorporated the use of large language models (LLMs) to synthesize current information in a time efficient manner. While LLMs offer value in streamlining data collection, further fine-tuning is necessary to align them with project-specific needs, which is typically the role of procurement experts.

The ranking of risks and effects relative to one another is another area for improvement. The current version is a preliminary attempt at prioritization, and future work should refine this ranking process to include or exclude certain effects more effectively. See the discussion of subject matter value judgement earlier in this discussion.

Additionally, the relative weighting of parameters in the risk formulas needs to be revisited. The integration of the five risk effects into a total supply chain vulnerability index (SCVI) score is a complex process, and fine-tuning the weightings of these parameters would enhance the robustness of the method. And for specific projects those relative weighting scores between the five risk effects may also change which therefore requires the attention when applying the method.

4. Supply Chain Risks require targeted mitigation

The appropriate level of risk mitigation depends on the type of risk identified. An important consideration is how to address risks in situations where the project team has limited influence, such as when the issue lies with a contracted supplier. Typically, contracts between the OEM are designed to minimize the risks exposed to, but developing strategies to mitigate risks beyond direct control will remain key.

5. Translating procurement risk into project planning should be done with care

Finally, the useful integration of supply chain risks into overall (level one) project planning remains a challenge. While this study has illustrated the application of the method using a single component in an example project of infrastructure development, real-world projects involve numerous components that all need to be delivered on time, and each with its own supply chain risks.

Expanding the method to effectively include more component procurement planning activities in a high level project planning will provide a more comprehensive view of how those various supply chain disruptions can impact the entire project schedule and how, both at an operational as well as a managerial level, those risks can be monitored.

6.1.4 Towards application and future developments of the method

Future validation through project application and subsequent the iterations of the method should incorporate dynamic elements, such as periodic updates and time-dependencies of supply chain characteristics such as technology readiness currently maturing through R&D activities, to better account for changing external conditions. Additionally, expanding the analysis to include more components, services, and supplier relationships will make the method more applicable to hydrogen infrastructure projects.

By addressing the limitations and suggested improvements, the presented risk management method could become a valuable tool in ensuring the resilience and readiness of hydrogen infrastructure in the Netherlands.

6.2 Discussion of the results from a Distribution System Operator point of view

In this discussion paragraph the specific regional Distribution System Operator, DSOs, (Alliander, Enexis and Stedin) perspective is discussed. This discussion is the result of three expert consultation and group discussions with representatives of the Dutch DSOs. Those representatives have backgrounds in procurement, contract management, innovation and strategy and new business development.

6.2.1 High level component supply chain risk assessment of DSO specific components

The first step of the risk assessment, determining which components are required, is done qualitatively in the SBS below (Figure 38). Part of the supply chain characteristics have been assessed during expert consultation workshops which resulted in two supply chain risk overviews. The risk levels are qualitatively shown in Figures 39 using the 5 effect categories, and additional details regarding six supply chain characteristics are provided in Figure 40.

The insights that were collected during the expert discussions are documented in the next section.

Figure 38 High level hydrogen system breakdown structure focussing on components operated by DSOs

Legend		E1: sourcing	E2: flow destination	E3: Routing	E4: Flow volume	E5: value density
Acceptable						
Potential risks						
Supply chain risks						
Unknown						
DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM COMPONENTS						
Metering	Household consumer flow meters (ultrasonic and balge)					Measurement Instrument Directive (MID) approval required. Has long leadtime.
	Small industrial flow meter					EVHI (volume conversion devices) required but not yet available for hydrogen gas group. Atax approval required for EVHIs which as long leadtime.
Pipelines & appendages	Low pressure (<200 mbar) PVC	Only two suppliers currently available for niche product				
	Low pressure (<200 mbar) PE					
	Medium pressure (200 mbar up to 8 bar)					
	High pressure (16 bar)					Unknown supply chain characteristics as DSOs currently have no 16 bar steel pipeline systems in use
	Pipeline closures					
Stations	Delivery station				High market capacities of OEMs but stable demand required to match production output with market demand.	Current natural gas components require minor adaptations to facilitate hydrogen gas use. Current pilot projects in the Netherlands running to test those components.
	Transfer station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station
	District station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station
	Booster station					

Figure 39 DSO hydrogen component risk identification for 5 effect categories

		Typical market position of component OEM (\$)				ESG	SEA	TRL	Certification	Scalability potential index
		Firm's size	Small	Medium	Large					
		Limited market scope	1	3	2					
		Extended	2	4	4					
DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM COMPONENTS										
Metering	Household consumer meters (ultrasonic and badge)							Small changes required (e.g. chips in ultrasonic meters)	Recognition on international and national (Netherlands metrology institute) is essential.	
	Small industrial meter								Recognition on international and national (Netherlands metrology institute) is essential.	
Pipelines & appendages	Low pressure (<200 mbar) PVC		Only two suppliers currently available for niche product					Local production required to prevent bulk transport		PE can substitute PVC. PE more costly component material
	Low pressure (<200 mbar) PE							Local production required to prevent bulk transport		
	Medium pressure (200 mbar up to 8 bar)									
	High pressure (16 bar)									
Stations										
	Pipeline dosures									
	Delivery station							Current natural gas components require minor adaptations to facilitate hydrogen gas use. Current pilot projects in the Netherlands running to test those components.		
	Transfer station			Similar components to delivery station				Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station
	District station			Similar components to delivery station				Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station	Similar components to delivery station
	Booster station									

Figure 40 DSO hydrogen component risk identification details on six characteristics

6.2.2 Discussion of DSO specific insights

Four discussion points are raised when reflecting on the SCRM approach from a DSO perspective:

1. The formal role for DSOs regarding hydrogen distribution is unclear

The role of Dutch (DSOs) in the hydrogen economy remains unclear. Currently, no specific targets have been set at the DSO level for hydrogen distribution infrastructure realization. This results in a lack of clarity regarding the functions of a future hydrogen distribution network, and subsequently a lack of clarity regarding the specific components that would supply those functions. An example of unclear functions and DSO roles is whether they will have a gas distribution role or will also be tasked with balancing and monitoring gas pressure and quality. Additionally, there is a lack of clarity on whether new systems are needed for these components, such as digitalization systems for control and monitor functions that would shift a passive "dumb" pipeline network to smart distribution systems.

The possible design choice for a dual gas DSO infrastructure is also a major concern. Dual gas distribution systems would handle both natural gas and hydrogen which can be seen as desirable to avoid the complexity of multiple infrastructure systems developed in parallel. DSO infrastructure does currently not use multiple pipelines in parallel as is common practice for several TSO grids in Europe.

While DSOs currently have no regulated role or activities related to hydrogen, new business initiatives such as by a sister company of a Dutch DSO in Amsterdam indicate a potential shift in this direction.

2. Forecasting results in unpractically large spreads of component quantities and timelines.

A more accurate outlook, both in terms of component quantity and timing, for the projected DSO hydrogen component needs is required before component supply chain risks can be assessed.

An unclear role in the Dutch energy transition inevitably leads to the disability to make (sufficiently) narrow forecasts of the amount of components that would be needed for the DSO infrastructure development and planning. While lower-pressure systems (up to 16 bar) with lower technological complexity than high pressure (60+ bar) are anticipated, a variety of components with specific requirements, such as the use of steel based 16-bar pipelines, is unfamiliar terrain for DSOs.

In addition to the large range of amounts of components possibly required, the timeline of DSO-level hydrogen infrastructure is also clouded in uncertainty. While full-scale national implementation is not expected before 2030-2035 due to a lack of decentral hydrogen gas demand. And multiple transition pathways could emerge from the current energy transition developments, e.g. central-to-decentral or vice versa, or admix-based, increasing the hydrogen gas content over time. Clarity regarding this transition pathway is essential in assessing the type and specifications of components needed, their quantity and that components supply chain risks.

3. Existing component suppliers and pilot project relations

Existing relationships with smaller original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) and EU suppliers offer a starting point for discussing components for hydrogen systems, including certification requirements for known components. As is illustrated in the high level risk identification tables above, the majority of the natural gas components discussed are expected to comply with hydrogen gas requirements. These component supply chains are therefore an existing starting point.

However, if hydrogen distribution will be done under higher pressures (e.g. 16 bar) or components currently not in use are to be added (e.g. booster station) for which existing components are not suitable, new component OEM relationships need to be developed. This may lead to additional supply

chain risks for DSOs as the specifications of those component will need to be discussed in detail, the timing and amount at which those components are required is uncertain and these OEMs may need stable market projections before upscaling their manufacturing capacity if that is required.

Hydrogen distribution pilot projects conducted at the local level provide early insights into the component functionalities required and the potential suppliers for those components. But full-scale distribution system component functionalities and volumes will potentially require other types of OEMs and/or supplier cont(r)act, and the lack of clear forecasts for volumes and timelines makes it difficult to formalize contracts or collaborations. However, when components can be used for both natural gas and hydrogen gas, lower risks can be perceived as the dependency on a well-timed hydrogen transition point in time is eliminated.

4. Add service supply chain risks rooted in an upsweep in human capital needed

Engineering and construction activities related to new infrastructure and converting existing infrastructure to hydrogen will present a significant workload with specific expertise and the need for human capital. This includes external capacity and internal capacity, which will increase the pressure on the human capital of that industry as it scales up to meet future demand.

Adding the service supply chain risks in addition to component supply chain risks therefore is crucial for the DSOs.

7 Conclusions and recommendations

This study set out to explore and understand potential bottlenecks within the hydrogen transport component manufacturing supply chain, with the goal of enabling grid operators to manage risks and ensure timely infrastructure deployment pre-2030, as well as strategic procurement post-2030. Through this research, several critical insights emerged, shedding light on the maturity, scalability, and resilience of the supply chain, and how these factors might impact hydrogen infrastructure projects.

In conclusion: By adopting proactive and continuous risk management strategies, hydrogen project developers can navigate supply chain complexities and support the timely deployment of hydrogen infrastructure. The future success of hydrogen projects will depend on strategic procurement planning, risk identification, and collaboration between operational and strategic teams, ensuring that supply chain bottlenecks do not stand in the way of progress.

Specifically for compressors, burners and flow meters, which were analyzed in detail, the supply chain risk levels were judged acceptable from a sourcing, routing and flow volume perspective but judged vulnerable from a flow destination and value density perspective. These supply chains are concluded to be partially ready for major upscaling in synchronization with increasing demand globally.

Note that the entire method outlined in this study was conducted specifically for three key components—hydrogen burners, compressors, and flow meters. The method's validity was verified by determining the relative position of each component on the critical path, with input from industry experts. While this verification provides valuable insights, a more thorough analysis involving a broader range of components would increase the robustness and generalizability of the outcomes.

7.1 Conclusive answers to the research questions

RQ1: How mature, scalable, and resilient can hydrogen component manufacturing supply chains expected to be?

7.1.1 Supply Chain Maturity and Scalability

While the hydrogen component manufacturing supply chains for many components are fully mature due to the decades of private industrial use of hydrogen gas, our research indicates that potential scalability risks do require attention when infrastructure is developed at national scale.

Global demand for hydrogen-related technologies is growing, which may lead to an increasing number of countries competing for the same components produced globally. This introduces risks of supply shortages and delays, particularly if suppliers struggle to scale up production to meet both domestic and international demand. To better understand the factors underlying this potential shortage of components, an extensive supply chain risk assessment approach is developed and tested using case study material. This method is discussed in more detail below.

The maturity and scalability of components is integrated in the method. The assessment of supply chain resiliency, which covers the ability of a supply chain to respond quickly to operational disruptions, was not extensively covered due to the operational character of this topic.

RQ2: What consequences can these component supply chain characteristics have on the timely realization of hydrogen infrastructure projects?

7.1.2 Impact on Hydrogen Infrastructure Projects

The ability of supply chains to meet the demand directly affects the timely completion of hydrogen infrastructure projects. Availability of components is crucial to meeting project milestones, and delays

in procurement could severely hinder progress. Components like compressors, essential for transport and storage, must be delivered on time to ensure that project milestones are met. While supply chain constraints are a factor, other aspects in those projects, such as the permitting and regulatory processes and the detailed engineering of component designs, may prove to be more significant obstacles given their long lead times. As such, identifying and mitigating procurement risks remains crucial to prevent supply chain issues from becoming limiting factors. This is particularly important given that speeding up the public procurement timeline is difficult due to its steps and the associated lead times per step.

Figure 41 An example of an 'all risks fired' project procurement delay +250% situation

7.1.3 The need for Proactive Supply Chain Risk Management

A central finding of this research is that early-stage and continuous supply chain risk management is essential. The design of the supply chain and the contracted partners need to be set up as such that growing future component demands and associated supply-demand mismatches are effectively mitigated upfront. This study developed an interdisciplinary Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) approach, which was tested through several component-specific examples in a fictional project timeline. The approach integrates established tools such as scenario planning, stakeholder consultation, and risk management, offering a structured way to anticipate and mitigate risks.

The general maturity of these tools varies, with stakeholder consultation and risk management often already at the core of infrastructure project management. Scenario planning, supply chain data analysis and critical path planning, are getting increasingly more complex when considering multiple infrastructure projects that depend on each other and, together, will be function as a hydrogen transport network.

7.1.4 Additional Considerations: certification and project realization timelines

An additional factor that emerged during this research is the role of certification. Component certification can introduce significant delays, particularly if the certification process is not yet completed and requires developments and alignment with certifying bodies. When this timeline is not accommodated for in project timelines, unexpected delays beyond the production of the component itself may emerge. Ensuring that components meet necessary norms and standards well in advance is a key strategy to mitigate these delays.

7.1.5 Conclusions regarding the supply chain risk management approach

The approach discussed and tested in this study offer its users a collection of tools and methods to use for supply risk mitigation purposes. This enables us to answer research question 3 below.

RQ3 - What specific actions stakeholders can take to mitigate component supply risks?

The research presents a combination of methods that stakeholders can adopt to safeguard the availability of critical components. This five-step approach, as illustrated in the visual framework below, outlines a novel approach for strategic procurement management.

Figure 42 The five-step approach to assess supply chain risk in project planning

- 1. The Need for Components:** The first step is to establish a clear understanding of the amount of necessary components over time, and identifying those components (or parts of that component) that may be critical for the hydrogen infrastructure. The availability of certain essential components, such as compressors, can directly impact project timelines, necessitating early engagement with suppliers and a comprehensive demand forecasts.
- 2. Component Trade Flow Analysis:** This step helps stakeholders analyze the international flow of components and key variables affecting supply chains. Factors such as market share, firm reliability, and production capacity must be assessed to anticipate potential delays or disruptions. This stage allows for the quantification of risks based on country, firm and component-level data, factoring in elements such as production capacity globally and trade relations between the Netherlands and the countries in which the manufacturing supply chains are located.

Figure 43 Data flow from supply chain characteristics to 5 risk effects and aggregated supply chain vulnerability index

3. **OEM and SCM Expert Consultation:** Engaging directly with Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs) and Supply Chain Management (SCM) experts is crucial for developing an informed perspective on component and manufacturing readiness. Such consultations ensure that data and information gathered is validated.
4. **Risk Assessment:** Building on the previous steps, a structured risk assessment can identify and quantify vulnerabilities within the supply chain by means of the Supply Chain Vulnerability Index consisting of many individual variables developed in this study. This assessment integrates supply chain risks into project planning to pinpoint which component supply chain characteristics are most likely to cause delays or affect project success.
5. **Component Procurement on the Critical Path:** Finally, integrating the risk assessment into the overall (level one) project timeline is vital to illustrate the vulnerability of the overall project success to well-managed supply chain risks. Procurement strategies should focus on ensuring that critical components are acquired in time to keep the overall project on track. By understanding which components and procurement activities are on the "critical path"—those without which the project cannot move forward—stakeholders can prioritize procurement decisions accordingly.

To further support this five-step process, the following tools and methods were used:

- **Scenario Planning:** This tool helps to explore the component requirements over time. The maturity of scenario planning in this context is medium and requires ongoing refinement to align with global and local developments around (the pace of) hydrogen infrastructure projects.
- **Stakeholder Consultation:** Regular interaction with industry players ensures that the procurement strategy remains responsive to market realities. Stakeholder consultation holds a high maturity level, having been frequently applied in large infrastructure projects.
- **Risk Management:** Proactive identification and mitigation of risks, both at the component and supply chain levels, are vital. This approach is well-established and highly mature in project-specific contexts.
- **Critical Path Planning:** Integrating supply chain risks into project timelines ensures that critical components are prioritized to avoid bottlenecks. While effective, this method still requires further refinement for hydrogen infrastructure projects as those projects are currently changing from private industry context to public contexts in which other types of factors and processes may determine the critical path.
- **Data Analysis:** Although data analysis holds low maturity in this specific of supply chain risk management, it has significant potential. By refining the Supply Chain Vulnerability Index, stakeholders can gain a clearer understanding of where supply chain risks may materialize.

A robust, proactive approach to supply chain risk management, combined with strategic procurement planning and cross-disciplinary collaboration, will be essential for achieving hydrogen infrastructure goals in a timely manner. The industry's adaptability, particularly in navigating the complexities of certification and supplier availability, will define its success pre-2030 and beyond.

7.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings from the discussion and conclusion, several strategic recommendations are proposed to enhance the resilience and readiness of the hydrogen infrastructure supply chain:

1. **Validate the Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM) approach by project applications**
The validation of the SCRM approach through its application to real-world projects with full project details is a critical next step. This would involve a detailed assessment of the chosen variables and

their respective weights to create project-specific insights into risk exposure. By applying this method continuously, rather than as a one-time activity, stakeholders can ensure that supply chain risks are consistently monitored and addressed throughout the lifecycle of hydrogen infrastructure projects. Early identification of potential risks allows for timely implementation of mitigation measures, reducing the likelihood of delays and cost overruns.

2. **Expand the scope of the Analysis step**

Future research should aim to broaden the scope of the analysis to include a wider range of hydrogen components and services. This will provide a more comprehensive understanding of the supply chain risks, particularly as the industry evolves. By expanding the dataset used for risk assessment, the reliability of the Supply Chain Vulnerability Index (SCVI) can be enhanced, allowing for more accurate identification of high-risk components or services. And expanding the analysis as such that it also accommodates the risk assessment services such as engineering and construction and special offshore vessels, which are crucial to the overall success of hydrogen infrastructure projects.

3. **Implement proactive Supply Chain Strategies for critical components and components with lower TRL**

To mitigate the risks identified in this study, proactive actions should be taken to reduce dependency on existing and emerging OEM ecosystems for hydrogen components. This can be achieved through collaborative research and development (R&D) programs with both private and public hydrogen infrastructure operators, fostering innovation and ensuring a steady supply of critical components. Furthermore, investments in long-lead-time assets, such as manufacturing capacity for key components, should be made upfront to safeguard against supply shortages that could jeopardize project timelines.

4. **Careful crafting of additional Supply Chain Strategies that complement the current strategies with risk-centered elements.**

A comprehensive assessment of the current supply chain strategy is essential to understand its strengths and weaknesses. Additionally, the desired future supply chain performance requirements must be clearly defined and align with the anticipated growth in hydrogen infrastructure projects globally. Additional supply chain strategies at the organization as well as the project level should be developed that builds on the existing strategy, retaining its effective components while addressing areas in need of improvement. This forward-looking strategy should prioritize resilience, scalability, and collaboration, ensuring that the supply chains of components can meet future demands reliably.

By implementing these recommendations, stakeholders in the hydrogen infrastructure sector can enhance their ability to navigate supply chain complexities and ensure the timely deployment of critical infrastructure, supporting the Netherlands' energy transition goals.

Appendix A) Component manufacturer market survey

Hydrogen Compressors

Company Name	Country (headquarter)	Market Scope	Reasoning for Market Scope	Size	Reasoning for Size
Atlas Copco	Sweden	Extended	Global recognition and leadership in the industry indicates broad market reach.	Large	Atlas Copco's extensive global operations and comprehensive product portfolio, combined with significant financial metrics, define it as a large company.
Burckhardt Compression	Switzerland	Extended	Technical expertise and global leadership in specialized compressors suggest a wide market reach.	Large	With a robust presence in global markets, supported by extensive service networks and innovative product solutions, Burckhardt Compression is categorized as large.
Haskel	USA	Limited	Focus on specific high-pressure technologies indicates a specialized but narrower market.	Medium	Significant investments for expansion, part of Ingersoll Rand.
Ingersoll Rand	USA	Extended	Comprehensive solutions and involvement across the value chain imply extensive market presence.	Large	Over 150 years in the market, global operations, and a range of strategic brands.
Bauer Compressors	USA	Extended	Specialization and active industry engagement suggest extensive market reach.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence (bauercomp) (bauercomp).
ABC Compressors	Spain	Limited	Custom solutions targeting specific sectors suggest a more focused market scope.	Small	Based on the tailored approach and market reach (Fluidex).
Aerzen	Germany	Extended	Innovation and efficient technologies indicate a significant market influence and reach.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company (AERZEN Headquarter).
Siemens	Germany	Extended	Established global leadership and experience indicate a broad market scope.	Large	Over 2500 units in operation indicate a large enterprise (Home).
Hydro-Pac	USA	Limited	Specialization in custom solutions for specific needs indicates a more focused market scope.	Small	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.

Ingersoll Rand A/S	USA	Extended	Comprehensive offerings and strong market presence imply broad market reach.	Large	Part of Ingersoll Rand group, indicating a substantial market presence and resources.
Mitsubishi Heavy Industries	Japan	Extended	Investment in advanced technologies and key role in production technologies suggest extensive market reach.	Large	Extensive involvement in large-scale hydrogen projects and significant investments in technology development suggest a large enterprise (Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Ltd.) (solutions.mhi).
Fornovagas	Italy	Extended	Commitment to innovation and customization indicates broad market appeal and reach.	Medium	Over 50 years of experience and significant industry presence (Fornovo Gas).
Bumhan Industries	South Korea	Limited	Strong domestic presence and niche international recognition suggest a more limited but significant impact.	Medium	Strong innovation focus and international recognition, indicating a growing presence in the industry.
Howden Group	United Kingdom	Extended	Wide product range and engineering reputation indicate extensive market scope.	Large	Global operational scale and comprehensive product range indicate a significant market influence.
Kaji Technology	Japan	Limited	Strong presence in Japan with high specialization suggests a focused but impactful market.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development (International Pavilion).
Xi'an Shaangu Power	China	Extended	Manufacturing and distribution capabilities suggest a broad market reach.	Large	Over 3,540 employees and a broad range of products with domestic and international distribution (MarketScreener).
Gardner Denver Nash	USA	Extended	Comprehensive product range and industry recognition suggest a wide market scope.	Large	Established industry presence and extensive product lineup imply a large company size
HAUG Sauer Kompressoren AG	Switzerland	Extended	Specialization in essential hydrogen compressor technologies indicates significant market influence.	Medium	Established niche supplier with a comprehensive range of products for specific gas handling applications (Sauer Compressors) (Sauer Compressors USA, Inc.).
NEUMAN & ESSER GROUP	Germany	Extended	Long history and comprehensive hydrogen solutions imply extensive market reach.	Large	Global presence, extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base (NEUMAN & ESSER).

Endress+Hauser AG	Switzerland	Extended	Comprehensive solutions and strong presence in the hydrogen measurement and control market indicate broad market reach.	Large	Extensive global operations, broad product offerings, and significant financial metrics suggest a large company size.
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Fiscal hydrogen flow meters

Company Name	Country (headquarter)	Market Scope	Reasoning for Market Scope	Size	Reasoning for Size
Emerson	USA	Extended	Manufactures the Micro Motion series and Rosemount ultrasonic meters, known for high accuracy and reliability in hydrogen applications.	Large	Extensive global operations and comprehensive product portfolio, combined with significant financial metrics, define it as a large company.
Rheonik	Germany	Extended	Specializes in high-pressure Coriolis meters for hydrogen fuel dispensing and renewable energy systems.	Large	Robust presence in global markets, supported by extensive service networks and innovative product solutions, categorize it as large.
KROHNE	Germany	Extended	Offers the OPTIMASS series, highly accurate for low-density hydrogen measurement in industrial applications.	Large	Global recognition and leadership in the industry indicate broad market reach and significant company size.
KOBOLD	Germany	Extended	Provides high-pressure Coriolis flow meters like the TMU-W model, designed for hydrogen gas applications.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Yokogawa	Japan	Extended	Produces versatile Coriolis meters for measuring mass flow, density, and temperature in hydrogen distribution.	Large	Over 150 years in the market, global operations, and a range of strategic brands.
Endress+Hauser	Switzerland	Extended	Manufactures Promass Coriolis meters, offering high precision for hydrogen gas applications.	Large	Innovation and global sustainability goals suggest a significant market presence and large size.
Siemens	Germany	Extended	Offers high-precision Coriolis and ultrasonic flow meters suitable for various hydrogen gas applications.	Large	Established global leadership and experience indicate a broad market scope and large enterprise size.
ABB	Switzerland	Extended	Provides reliable Coriolis flow meters used in hydrogen and other industrial gas applications.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.

Bronkhorst	Netherlands	Extended	Specializes in low-flow Coriolis meters, ideal for laboratory and precise industrial hydrogen measurements.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Brooks Instrument	USA	Extended	Offers a range of flow meters including Coriolis, thermal mass, and variable area meters for hydrogen applications.	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
Azbil	Japan	Extended	Provides Coriolis mass flow meters with high accuracy for hydrogen and other gases in industrial applications.	Large	Comprehensive product portfolio and significant financial metrics indicate a large company size.
Alicat Scientific	USA	Extended	Manufactures mass flow meters that measure hydrogen with high accuracy and response time for various applications.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Sierra Instruments	USA	Extended	Offers high-accuracy thermal mass flow meters for hydrogen, suitable for low to medium flow rates.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Mass Flow ONLINE	Netherlands	Extended	Specializes in online sales of high-precision flow meters, including Coriolis meters for hydrogen gas.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Sensirion	Switzerland	Extended	Manufactures thermal mass flow meters and modules for hydrogen and other gas mixtures, featuring low power consumption and high accuracy.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Turbines, Inc.	USA	Extended	Produces turbine flow meters known for reliability and accuracy in hydrogen gas and other industrial applications.	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
Omega Engineering	USA	Extended	Offers a variety of mass flow meters for hydrogen and other gases, known for ease of use and reliability.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Panametrics	USA	Extended	Provides ultrasonic and flare flow meters, ideal for measuring hydrogen and other gases in challenging environments.	Large	Global recognition and leadership in the industry indicate broad market reach and significant company size.

TRICOR Coriolis Technology	USA	Extended	Manufactures high-pressure Coriolis flow meters for hydrogen applications, including the TCMH 0450 model.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
SICK	Germany	Extended	Offers ultrasonic flow meters for hydrogen and hydrogen-methane mixtures, ensuring reliable and accurate measurements.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Chart Industries	USA	Extended	Provides the Flowcom® series for liquid and gaseous hydrogen, known for maintenance-free operation and high accuracy.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
ABLE Instruments	UK	Extended	Distributes Rheonik Coriolis mass flow meters and other flow measurement solutions for high-pressure hydrogen applications.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
MATHESON	USA	Extended	Offers a broad range of flow meters and controllers for hydrogen, including Coriolis and thermal mass flow meters.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
TotalEnergies	France	Extended	Provides certified hydrogen dispensers for commercial and passenger vehicles, supporting high-pressure hydrogen fueling stations.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
McCrometer	USA	Extended	Produces V-Cone advanced differential pressure meters for various applications, including steam and gas flow measurement.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Fluid Components International (FCI)	USA	Extended	Provides the ST100 Series thermal mass flow meters, ideal for hydrogen gas production and industrial applications.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
ATO Flow Meter	China	Extended	Manufactures a wide range of flow meters including magnetic, vortex, liquid turbine, and gas mass flow meters suitable for hydrogen.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.

Acorn Controls	India	Extended	Produces ultrasonic flow meters and hydrogen gas detectors, offering solutions for various industrial applications.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Badger Meter	USA	Extended	Provides turbine flow meters for liquids and gases, including models for high-accuracy measurement in hydrogen applications.	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
Horiba	Japan	Extended	Specializes in precision instruments including mass flow controllers and meters suitable for hydrogen gas measurement.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Kofloc	Japan	Extended	Offers mass flow controllers and meters designed for accurate measurement of hydrogen and other gases in various industries.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Azbil Corporation	Japan	Extended	Provides advanced measurement and control solutions, including Coriolis mass flow meters for hydrogen gas.	Large	Comprehensive product portfolio and significant financial metrics indicate a large company size.
Yokogawa Electric	Japan	Extended	Produces a wide range of flow meters including Coriolis and thermal mass flow meters for precise hydrogen gas measurement.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Fuji Electric	Japan	Extended	Manufactures ultrasonic and Coriolis flow meters suitable for hydrogen and other industrial gases.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
KROHNE China	China	Extended	Provides the OPTIMASS series of Coriolis flow meters, known for their accuracy in hydrogen measurement.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Baker Hughes (Panametrics)	USA	Extended	Offers ultrasonic and other flow meters for hydrogen measurement, ensuring reliable performance in various industrial settings.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Keyence	Japan	Extended	Known for its high-precision flow sensors and meters used in	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major

			hydrogen and other gas applications.		hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
Hitachi High-Tech	Japan	Extended	Manufactures advanced measurement instruments including mass flow meters for hydrogen gas.	Large	Innovation and global sustainability goals suggest a significant market presence and large size.
Energoflow AG	Switzerland	Extended	Provides ultrasonic flow meters for gas applications, including hydrogen and hydrogen-methane mixtures. Their meters are known for high accuracy and reliability.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
KROHNE Group	Germany	Extended	Offers advanced ultrasonic and Coriolis flow meters suitable for hydrogen gas measurement in various industrial applications.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
ELIS PLZEN	Czech Republic	Extended	Offers ultrasonic and induction flow meters for various applications, including hydrogen gas measurement.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Aalborg	Germany	Extended	Manufactures a variety of flow meters, including thermal mass and variable area flow meters, suitable for hydrogen and other industrial gases.	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
FLOMEC	Australia	Extended	Specializes in a wide range of flow meters including turbine, ultrasonic, and positive displacement flow meters for various applications.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Emerson AU	Australia	Extended	Provides Rosemount ultrasonic flow meters for gas and liquid applications, ensuring high accuracy and reliability for hydrogen measurement.	Large	Extensive product and service offerings, involvement in major hydrogen projects, and significant employee base.
Swagelok	USA	Extended	Offers a variety of flow measurement and control products, including those suitable for hydrogen gas applications.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Manas Microsystems	India	Extended	Manufactures a variety of flow meters including electromagnetic, ultrasonic, and thermal	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum

			mass flow meters, serving global markets including Australia and New Zealand.		suggest a medium-sized company.
ANZIGA	Australia	Extended	Represents major industrial gas producers, promoting safety and standards in the use, storage, and transportation of gases including hydrogen.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Flow Meter Group	Netherlands	Extended	Provides a variety of flow meters, including turbine and rotary gas meters, certified by Dutch NMI and compliant with EU and OIML directives.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Elster-Instromet	Belgium	Extended	Provides a range of gas flow meters, including those suitable for hydrogen, with a focus on precision and reliability in industrial settings.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Energas Technologies	South Africa	Extended	Specializes in gas flow meters including ultrasonic meters for precise measurement in various applications such as gas distribution and power generation.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Afrox	South Africa	Extended	Provides a range of gas equipment including regulators, flow meters, and accessories for industrial gas applications.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
Action Instruments SA	South Africa	Extended	Offers a variety of flow measurement devices including thermal mass flow meters and Pitot tube flow sensors for industrial applications.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Yokogawa South Africa	South Africa	Extended	Provides a range of flow meters including variable area (VA) and ultrasonic flow meters suitable for hydrogen and other industrial gases.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and global market reach, with cutting-edge product development.
Acorn Controls Private Limited	India	Extended	Manufacturer of various flow meters including ultrasonic flow meters and hydrogen gas detectors, serving OEMs and industrial applications.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.

Prism Instrumentation	India	Extended	Offers a range of flow meters including Coriolis, ultrasonic, and vortex flow meters for various industrial applications.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Burak Metering	India	Extended	Provides a wide range of flow meters including thermal mass flow meters for natural gas and biogas, emphasizing accuracy and reliability.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Creative Engineers	India	Extended	Manufacturer and exporter of flow meters with a global reach, offering high-quality products for diverse industrial applications.	Medium	Innovative solutions and a broad application spectrum suggest a medium-sized company.
Sunflow Technologies	India	Extended	Trusted supplier of flow meters, known for their exceptional quality and serving prestigious clients across various industries.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.
Aman Engineering Works	India	Extended	Established manufacturer of flow meters, providing high standards of engineering and reliable products for industrial use.	Medium	Customization and specialization suggest a smaller, focused operation.

Hydrogen burners

Company Name	Country (Headquarters)	Market Scope	Reasoning for Market Scope	Size	Reasoning for Size
Zeeco Inc.	USA	Extended	Known for advanced combustion solutions, including hydrogen burners.	Large	Extensive global operations and comprehensive product portfolio.
Elco Burners	Germany	Extended	Specializes in low NOx combustion systems and hydrogen burners.	Large	Strong presence in Europe and established industry expertise.
Industrial Combustion	USA	Extended	Provides industrial burners designed for hydrogen applications.	Large	Broad product offerings and an established industry presence.
John Zink Hamworthy	USA	Extended	Offers hydrogen-capable burners for various industrial applications.	Large	Extensive global reach and a leader in combustion technology.
Honeywell UOP	USA	Extended	Develops hydrogen burners and related technologies.	Large	Significant market presence and a comprehensive product portfolio.
Faber Burner Company	USA	Extended	Produces industrial burners, including those for hydrogen.	Large	Established reputation and broad market reach.

Maxon (Honeywell Company)	USA	Extended	Known for high-efficiency industrial burners including hydrogen.	Large	Extensive product range and significant industry impact.
Forney Corporation	USA	Extended	Specializes in industrial combustion and hydrogen burner solutions.	Large	Broad industry application and a significant global footprint.
Ecostar Burners	Italy	Extended	Provides hydrogen-ready industrial burners.	Medium	Known for innovation and specialization in burner technology.
Bloom Engineering	USA	Extended	Focuses on industrial burners for hydrogen and other gases.	Medium	Innovation in combustion technology and strong industry presence.
ESA Pyronics International	Italy	Extended	Offers a range of industrial burners suitable for hydrogen.	Medium	Specialized solutions and significant market reach in Europe.
Tokyo Gas	Japan	Extended	Pioneers in hydrogen combustion technology with regenerative burners.	Large	Established leader in the energy sector with extensive expertise.
Babcock & Wilcox	USA	Extended	Supplies burners for utility-scale power boilers using hydrogen.	Large	Long-standing industry presence and innovative hydrogen solutions.
SGD Pharma	France	Extended	Successfully trialed hydrogen burners in industrial glass production.	Large	Leading global presence in the pharmaceutical packaging industry.
Fives Group	France	Extended	Offers hydrogen-compatible burners for various industrial applications.	Large	Known for engineering and industrial expertise worldwide.
Air Liquide	Japan	Extended	Provides hydrogen burner technology and support for industrial applications.	Large	Global leader in industrial gases and services with extensive operations in Asia.
Osaka Gas	Japan	Extended	Develops hydrogen-compatible burners for various industrial applications.	Large	Significant presence in the energy sector with a focus on innovation.
Rinnai Corporation	Japan	Extended	Manufactures hydrogen-ready heating solutions, including burners.	Large	Known for advanced heating technologies and a wide market reach.
Hyundai Heavy Industries	South Korea	Extended	Produces hydrogen-compatible burners for industrial and marine applications.	Large	Leading global shipbuilder and industrial equipment manufacturer.
E&M Combustión	Spain	Extended	Specializes in hydrogen combustion systems for industrial use.	Medium	Focuses on innovative and sustainable hydrogen combustion technologies.
Zantingh	Netherlands	Extended	Specialized in professional gas burner systems, central heating components, flue gas condensers, heat exchangers and CO2 dosing systems and related services.	Medium	internationally operating company
Monarch	Netherlands	Extended	Specializes in (Weishaupt) burners, boilers and heatpumps.	Large	Related to Weishaupt organization.

Stork Thermeq	Netherlands	Extended	Supplies with (Ultra) Low NOx burners for gaseous, liquid and solid fuels, renewables and hydrogen, both for direct fired installations as well as supplementary firing.	Large	Global operations
Instalat	Netherlands	Extended	Designs, supplies and commissions tunnel kilns for the heavy clay industry as well as for other parts of ceramic engineering.	Medium	Focusses on ceramics sector. Innovative in hydrogen combustion.

Appendix B) Variables used: Component Trade Flow Analysis

The used variables are categorized into one of three larger sets of variables. Namely; firm, county or component specific variables.

Firm Specific variables

We have two firm specific variables; their estimated market share, and their Environmental Social Government Index.

Market Share

Firm i 's market share, S_i is a function of the firm's market position and size. It is estimated as follow;

$$S_i = \frac{X_i}{\sum_{i=0}^n X_i} 100$$

Where X_i is;

		Firm's size		
		Small	Medium	Large
Firm's Market scope	Limited	1	1,5	2
	Extended	2	3	4

Methodology on determining firm's size and position

Data on the firm i 's size and market position are derived by using AI tools (ChatGPT and Gemini) and validated with market- and TNO experts.

Environmental Social Governance Index

The Environmental Social Governance (ESG) Index is a measure used to evaluate a company's collective conscientiousness for social and environmental factors. It is used by investors to assess potential investment risks and growth opportunities, focusing on sustainability and ethical impacts of an investment. The index considers how a corporation performs as a steward of the natural environment, manages relationships with employees, suppliers, customers, and communities, and practices good governance, like leadership, audits, internal controls, and shareholder rights.

Country specific variables

Country-level variables capture broad characteristics and external conditions that influence a nation's geopolitical and economic behavior, specifically focusing on the countries where the firms in question are headquartered. These variables encompass governance, trade, culture, and logistical factors that shape the international relationships and economic activities of these nations. For example, the World Governance Index evaluates the quality of governance across multiple dimensions, such as political stability and corruption control. Trade restrictions imposed by entities like the European Union and existing trade relations reveal economic dependencies. Additionally, cultural differences and logistical

risks, such as maritime dangers, help assess the challenges these countries face in cross-border interactions and supply chains, which directly impact the operations of the firms headquartered there.

World Government Index

The World Governance Index (WGI) is a data set that measures the governance quality of over 200 countries. It's based on perceptions of governance collected from enterprises, citizens, and expert respondents. The WGI looks at governance through six dimensions:

1. **Voice and Accountability:** This refers to the citizens' ability to participate in government selection, as well as the existence of freedom of expression, association, and a free press.
2. **Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism:** This examines the likelihood of destabilization or overthrow of the government by unconstitutional or violent means, including terrorism.
3. **Government Effectiveness:** This captures the quality of public services and civil service, the quality of policy formulation and implementation, and the credibility of the government's commitment to policies.
4. **Regulatory Quality:** This assesses the ability of the government to create and implement sound policies that promote private sector development.
5. **Rule of Law:** This indicates the extent to which society abides by the legal framework, including contract enforcement, property rights, the police, and the judiciary.
6. **Control of Corruption:** This measures the use of public power for private benefit, including both minor and grand corruption and state capture.

To transform the Worldwide Governance Indicators, which are on a scale from roughly -2.5 to 2.5, to a 0-1 index, you first shift the scale up by adding 2.5. Then, you rescale to 0-1 by dividing the result by 5. This process maintains the relative standings and differences but presents them in a standard index form where 1 represents the best governance score possible and 0 the worst.

EU imposed trade restrictions

The European Union employs trade sanctions as part of its foreign policy to address conflicts, uphold human rights, and support international law. These sanctions can be aimed at specific countries, entities, or individuals and may include various restrictive measures such as import and export bans, asset freezes, and travel restrictions. The EU has a range of sanctions in place, with over 30 different regimes targeting various issues worldwide. The most current and detailed list of EU-imposed trade sanctions, including specific measures and targeted entities or countries, is available on the EU Sanctions Map website ([sanctionsmap](#)).

Existing trade relations

Existing trade relationships are relevant for assessing the Netherlands' economic interdependence with other countries by quantifying the proportion of imports from a specific country relative to its total imports. This proxy is valuable for understanding the economic ties and dependencies between the Netherlands and other nations.

To calculate this variable, we use two data sources: the first draws on customs data to capture the total value of all imports from a specific country to the Netherlands²²; the second utilizes Prodcop²³

²² <https://www.belastingdienst.nl/wps/wcm/connect/en/customs/customs>

²³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/prodcom/database>

data, which details the import of specific types of goods. For the analysis using Prodcum data, we focus on a specific basket of goods, identified by the particular component in question. This allows for a precise examination of import patterns related to specialized goods categories.

However, Prodcum data does not provide information for all countries. When available, we prioritize this data for a detailed analysis of specific goods. If Prodcum data is unavailable, we resort to customs data, which covers all countries and provides a broader overview of the Netherlands' import landscape.

We take the total value of imports from the specific country (as per customs data) and divide it by the total value of all imports into the Netherlands. Similarly, for the specific Prodcum basket of goods, we calculate the total value of imports of those goods and divide it by the total value of all imports into the Netherlands. The result from each dataset is then multiplied by 100 to express it as a percentage, providing a clear view of economic dependencies either in general or specific to certain goods.

Cultural Difference

The Cultural difference is a numerical value that quantifies the cultural disparity between the Netherlands and another nation, using four of Hofstede's cultural dimensions: Power Distance, Individualism, Motivation towards achievement and success, and Uncertainty Avoidance. (For more information see: <https://www.hofstede-insights.com/>)

- This variable is useful for understanding how culturally similar or different a country is from the Netherlands, which can inform decisions in international business, diplomacy, and cross-cultural research.

We calculate it as follows: For each of the four dimensions, we first calculate the absolute difference between the Netherlands' score and the score of the country in question. We then sum these absolute differences to get a total score. To normalize the score on a scale from 0 to 1, where 0 represents no difference and 1 represents the maximum possible cultural difference, we divide the total score by 400 (since each dimension can contribute a maximum difference of 100).

Logistic Maritime Risks

We analyse the presence of potential risks along the shortest sea route from firm *i*'s headquarters' host country to the Netherlands. We focus on three types of maritime risks; the presence of potential choke points, the presence of potential piracy points; and the presence of potential severe weather points.

We have identified 10 potential choke points, 10 potential piracy points, and 5 potential severe weather points. They are presented in the following three tables, respectively.

Potential Choke points
1. Strait of Hormuz - Connects the Persian Gulf with the Gulf of Oman, and is a crucial passage for oil transportation.
2. Strait of Malacca - Located between the Malay Peninsula and the Indonesian island of Sumatra, it is one of the busiest waterways in the world and a key route for trade between the Indian Ocean and the Pacific Ocean.
3. Suez Canal - Connects the Mediterranean Sea to the Red Sea and provides a shortcut for ships traveling between Europe and Asia.
4. Bab el Mandeb - Connects the Red Sea to the Gulf of Aden and is a strategic chokepoint for ships traveling to and from the Suez Canal.
5. Bosphorus Strait - Connects the Black Sea to the Mediterranean Sea and serves as a key passage for trade between Europe and Asia.
6. Strait of Gibraltar - Connects the Mediterranean Sea to the Atlantic Ocean and is a vital route for shipping between Europe and Africa.
7. Danish Straits - Consisting of the Øresund, Great Belt, and Little Belt straits, they connect the Baltic Sea to the North Sea and are important for maritime trade in Northern Europe.
8. Taiwan Strait - Separates the island of Taiwan from mainland China and is a politically sensitive waterway.
9. Mozambique Channel - Lies between Madagascar and the southeastern coast of Africa and is a significant route for shipping between the Indian Ocean and the Atlantic Ocean.
10. Torres Strait - Located between Australia and Papua New Guinea, it is a narrow passage for ships traveling between the Pacific Ocean and the Indian Ocean.

Potential piracy points
1. Gulf of Aden - Located between Yemen and Somalia, it has been a hotspot for piracy, particularly in the waters off the coast of Somalia. However, international naval patrols have significantly reduced piracy in recent years.
2. Sulu and Celebes Seas - Situated between the Philippines, Indonesia, and Malaysia, this area has seen piracy incidents, often attributed to groups like the Abu Sayyaf Group operating in the region.
3. Straits of Malacca and Singapore - While primarily a major shipping route, incidents of piracy have occurred in these narrow straits due to the high volume of maritime traffic passing through.
4. Niger Delta - Off the coast of Nigeria, piracy has been a persistent issue, often involving attacks on oil tankers and other vessels for ransom or theft.
5. Gulf of Guinea - Stretching along the coast of West Africa, particularly around Nigeria, Benin, and Togo, piracy incidents, including hijackings and kidnappings, have been reported.
6. Bay of Bengal - Near the coasts of India, Bangladesh, Myanmar, and Sri Lanka, there have been reports of piracy and maritime crime, including attacks on fishing vessels and cargo ships.
7. Seychelles and Maldives - These island nations in the Indian Ocean have experienced occasional piracy incidents, although they have mostly been limited to attempts to rob yachts and tourist boats.
8. Sunda Strait - Between the Indonesian islands of Java and Sumatra, piracy incidents have been reported due to its strategic location for maritime traffic.
9. Venezuelan Coast - Piracy incidents have been reported off the coast of Venezuela, particularly in the waters around the Gulf of Venezuela and the eastern coast near Trinidad and Tobago.
10. Somali Coast - While piracy has significantly decreased in recent years due to international naval patrols and increased security measures, occasional incidents still occur off the coast of Somalia.

Potential severe weather points
<p>1. Pacific Typhoon Basin (Western Pacific Ocean): Encompassing regions near Southeast Asia, including the Philippines, Indonesia, Malaysia, and Vietnam, as well as extending into the western Pacific, this basin experiences frequent occurrences of tropical cyclones, typhoons, heavy rainfall, flooding, and landslides due to its location in the tropical cyclone genesis area.</p>
<p>2. Bay of Bengal (Indian Ocean): Countries bordering the Bay of Bengal, such as Bangladesh, India, Myanmar, and Sri Lanka, are highly susceptible to severe weather events, including cyclones, heavy rainfall, storm surges, and flooding, particularly during the annual monsoon season (June to October), when the region experiences intense tropical cyclones and widespread devastation.</p>
<p>3. Cape of Good Hope (Southern Tip of Africa): This maritime region, located at the southern tip of Africa, is notorious for its volatile weather conditions, including strong winds, powerful storms, and rough seas. The convergence of the warm Agulhas Current and the cold Benguela Current in the region can lead to the formation of intense low-pressure systems and hazardous sailing conditions for maritime vessels.</p>
<p>4. Gulf of Mexico (Northwestern Caribbean Sea): The Gulf of Mexico is prone to tropical cyclone development, particularly during the Atlantic hurricane season (June to November). Coastal areas of countries bordering the Gulf, such as the United States (Texas, Louisiana, Mississippi, Alabama, Florida), Mexico, and Cuba, face the risk of hurricanes, storm surges, heavy rainfall, and inland flooding, posing significant threats to maritime operations, offshore drilling platforms, and coastal communities.</p>
<p>5. Cyclone Alley (Southwest Indian Ocean): Stretching across the southwestern Indian Ocean, Cyclone Alley encompasses regions near Madagascar, Mauritius, Reunion Island, and the Comoros. This area experiences frequent tropical cyclone activity, particularly during the austral summer months (November to April), leading to destructive winds, heavy rainfall, storm surges, and coastal erosion, affecting maritime navigation, fishing activities, and coastal infrastructure.</p>

The presences of potential maritime risk is simply calculated as the sum of the number of potential choke points, piracy points and/or severe weather points along the shortest sea route from that specific country to the Netherlands and divided by 25.

In the table below we provide an overview for a selection of countries.

Country	Choke Points	Piracy Points	Severe Weather Points Passed	Maritime Risk Index
China	Taiwan Strait > Strait of Malacca > Suez Canal > Strait of Dover	Sulu and Celebes Seas, Bay of Bengal, Sunda Strait	Pacific Typhoon Basin, Cyclone Alley (if via Indian Ocean)	0.36
Germany	None	None	None	0.00
Italy	Strait of Gibraltar > Strait of Dover	None	None	0.08
Japan	Taiwan Strait > Strait of Malacca > Suez Canal > Strait of Dover	Sulu and Celebes Seas, Bay of Bengal, Sunda Strait	Pacific Typhoon Basin	0.32
South Korea	Strait of Malacca > Suez Canal > Strait of Dover	Sulu and Celebes Seas, Bay of Bengal, Sunda Strait	None	0.24
Spain	Strait of Gibraltar > Strait of Dover	None	None	0.08
Switzerland	None	None	None	NA
United Kingdom	Strait of Dover	None	None	0.04
United States	Strait of Dover	None	None	0.04

Distance

The distance between a specific country and the Netherlands is estimated in kilometers over sea, using the shortest possible maritime route.

Landlocked

Understanding whether a country is landlocked is vital for supply chain planning because it directly impacts transportation costs and options. Here's the relevance of knowing a country's landlocked status:

1. **Transport Access:** Landlocked countries require overland routes to reach seaports, increasing logistical complexity and costs compared to countries with direct sea access.
2. **Neighbor Dependency:** Landlocked countries rely on neighboring countries for port access, which can complicate logistics and affect political and economic relations.
3. **Strategic Planning:** Companies must consider these factors when developing supply chain strategies, particularly in how they might affect costs, transit times, and the need for robust contingency planning.

In this context, we use a binary variable to indicate geographical access which equals 1 if the country is landlocked and 0 otherwise.

Component specific variables

Component-specific variables focus on the characteristics and logistical requirements tied to the production and transportation of individual industrial components. These variables assess factors such as whether a component requires maritime transport, its scalability potential based on existing infrastructure and technology, and its technology readiness level (TRL). Each of these variables offers insights into the practicality and challenges of manufacturing, distributing, and implementing specific components in industrial sectors. They help to analyze how easily a product can be scaled up, its maturity in the market, and its alignment with existing supply chains and technology.

SEA: Transport by water required

This is a binary variable that captures whether the component needs to be transported by vessel or can be transported overland or by plane.

Scalability Potential Index

The methodology outlined here aims to evaluate an industry's reliance on existing infrastructure and technology transfer to gauge how easily production can be scaled. This approach can be adapted to any sector that needs to evaluate its integration with established manufacturing capabilities and technological advancements. The index used ranges from 0 (no reliance) to 1 (full reliance).

Components of the Index

1. Infrastructure Utilization (Weight: 50%)

- **Physical Facilities:** Evaluates the extent to which current manufacturing facilities can produce the targeted product without significant modifications.
- **Supply Chains:** Assesses the readiness of existing supply chains to support production, considering the need for specific materials and components.

2. Technology Transfer (Weight: 50%)

- **Technological Similarity:** Measures how similar the technologies needed for the new product are to those currently in use in other applications within the industry.
- **Expertise and Knowledge Transfer:** Determines how much of the existing workforce knowledge and skills can be transferred to the production of the new product.

Each component is rated on a scale from 0 to 10 based on the degree of dependency. The scores for Physical Facilities and Supply Chains are averaged to determine the Infrastructure Utilization score. Similarly, Technological Similarity and Expertise and Knowledge Transfer are averaged to compute the Technology Transfer score.

The final index is calculated as follows;

$$SCAL_POT = \frac{(Infrastructure\ Utilization) + (Technology\ Transfer)}{40}$$

Scalability potential of Hydrogen Compressors

1. Infrastructure Utilization

- **Physical Facilities:** Compressor manufacturing often requires specific tooling and equipment, but the fundamental infrastructure is similar to other heavy industrial manufacturing setups. Modifications might be needed, particularly for compressors requiring higher precision or different pressure ratings.
 - **Estimated Value:** 7 (minor modifications are needed, but much of the existing infrastructure is adequate).
- **Supply Chains:** The compressor industry benefits from well-established supply chains that are capable of providing standard components like steel, valves, and electronic controls. However, specialized compressors might need components that are not as readily available.
 - **Estimated Value:** 6 (good existing supply chain but needs enhancements for specialized components).

2. Technology Transfer

- **Technological Similarity:** Most types of compressors share basic mechanical principles and designs, such as rotary or reciprocating mechanisms. While specific applications (like those required in highly regulated industries such as food or pharmaceuticals) might differ significantly, the core technology often remains similar.
 - **Estimated Value:** 8 (high technological similarity with slight modifications for specific applications).
- **Expertise and Knowledge Transfer:** The workforce in the compressor industry typically has a strong background in mechanical engineering and fluid dynamics, applicable across various types of compressors. Specialized training might be needed for niche applications or new technologies like oil-free or ultra-high-pressure systems.
 - **Estimated Value:** 7 (significant expertise transferable, with additional training required for specialized products).

Final Index Calculation

$$SCAL_POT_{compressors} = \frac{(7 + 6) + (8 + 7)}{40} = 0,7$$

Conclusion

An index value of 0,7 indicates a moderate to high degree of reliance on existing infrastructure and technology for the compressor industry. This suggests that the industry can relatively easily adapt and scale up production, leveraging its established manufacturing capabilities and technological base. The high score reflects an industry well-positioned to meet increasing demand or diversify into new compressor types with moderate investments in specific adaptations and workforce training. This reliance on existing structures implies that while new investments are necessary for expansion or specialization, the foundational capabilities strongly support growth and adaptation.

Scalability Potential of Hydrogen Flow Meters

1. Infrastructure Utilization○ **Physical Facilities:**

- Flow meter manufacturing involves precision engineering and often requires specialized machinery for tasks such as sensor integration, calibration, and testing. While some equipment might be shared with other types of precision instruments, dedicated lines for flow meters might be necessary to ensure quality and accuracy, especially for hydrogen applications.
- **Estimated Value: 8** (some specialized equipment is needed, but a significant portion of the existing infrastructure is suitable).

○ **Supply Chains:**

- The flow meter industry relies on a robust supply chain for materials such as metals, electronics, and sensors. The availability of specialized sensors for hydrogen flow measurement might require enhancements in the supply chain to ensure reliability and precision. Existing suppliers for similar technologies can be adapted, but additional certification and quality assurance processes might be needed.
- **Estimated Value: 7** (strong existing supply chain with some need for specialized components and quality assurance).

2. Technology Transfer○ **Technological Similarity:**

- The technology used in hydrogen flow meters shares similarities with other types of flow meters used for various gases and liquids. The principles of measurement (e.g., Coriolis, ultrasonic) remain the same, but they need to be adapted for the specific properties of hydrogen, such as its low density and high diffusivity.
- **Estimated Value: 8** (high similarity with existing technologies, but requires adaptation for hydrogen's unique properties).

○ **Expertise and Knowledge Transfer:**

2. The workforce skilled in flow meter technologies can transfer much of their expertise to hydrogen flow meters. However, additional training and development are required to handle the nuances of hydrogen measurement and ensure safety and accuracy.
3. **Estimated Value: 8** (significant expertise can be transferred with some additional training required).

Final Index Calculation

$$SCAL_{POT_{Meters}} = \frac{(8 + 7) + (8 + 8)}{40} = 0,775$$

Conclusion

An index value of 0.775 indicates a high degree of reliance on existing infrastructure and technology for the hydrogen flow meter industry. This suggests that the industry is well-equipped to scale up production, leveraging its established manufacturing capabilities and technological base. The high score reflects an industry that can meet increasing demand or diversify into new flow meter types with relatively minor investments in specific adaptations and workforce training. This reliance on existing structures implies that while some new investments are necessary for expansion or specialization, the foundational capabilities strongly support growth and adaptation.

Scalability Potential of Hydrogen Burners

1. Infrastructure Utilization

○ Physical Facilities:

- Manufacturing hydrogen burners involves specialized processes, including the integration of safety systems to handle hydrogen's high flammability. While some existing facilities for gas burner production can be adapted, significant modifications might be necessary to meet the stringent safety and performance requirements for hydrogen burners.
- **Estimated Value:** 6 (significant modifications needed to existing facilities to ensure safety and performance).

○ Supply Chains:

- The supply chains for hydrogen burners need to accommodate materials that can withstand high temperatures and corrosion from hydrogen combustion. While the base supply chain for burner components is well-established, additional requirements for materials and safety certifications might pose challenges.
- **Estimated Value:** 5 (existing supply chain needs significant enhancements for specialized materials and safety components).

Technology Transfer

2. Technology Transfer

○ Technological Similarity:

- The technology used in hydrogen burners is somewhat similar to other gas burners but requires significant adaptation due to hydrogen's unique combustion properties, such as its high flammability and low ignition energy. Technologies used in existing gas burners can be partially transferred, but substantial modifications are necessary.
- **Estimated Value:** 6 (moderate similarity with existing technologies, but substantial adaptations needed).

○ Expertise and Knowledge Transfer:

- The workforce skilled in gas burner technologies can transfer some of their knowledge to hydrogen burners. However, additional training is critical to address the safety, material, and combustion differences specific to hydrogen.
- **Estimated Value:** 6 (significant expertise can be transferred, but extensive additional training required).

Final Index Calculation

$$SCAL_{POT_{Burners}} = \frac{(6 + 5) + (6 + 6)}{40} = 0,575$$

Conclusion

An index value of 0.575 indicates a moderate degree of reliance on existing infrastructure and technology for the hydrogen burner industry. This suggests that while there is a foundation to build upon, significant enhancements and adaptations in both infrastructure and technology are needed to effectively scale up the production of hydrogen burners. The moderate score reflects an industry that can grow but will require targeted investments in specialized equipment, supply chain enhancements, and workforce training to meet the specific demands of hydrogen combustion.

TRL – Technology Readiness Level

The Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is a metric used to assess the maturity level of a particular technology. The TRL scale typically ranges from 1 to 9, with each level representing a stage in the development process:

1. Basic principles observed and reported
2. Technology concept and/or application formulated
3. Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof of concept
4. Component and/or breadboard validation in laboratory environment
5. Component and/or breadboard validation in relevant environment
6. System/subsystem model or prototype demonstration in a relevant environment
7. System prototype demonstration in an operational environment
8. Actual system completed and qualified through test and demonstration
9. Actual system proven through successful mission operations

As the technology progresses through each TRL level, it becomes closer to being fully developed and ready for practical use. This scale helps stakeholders understand the level of risk associated with adopting a particular technology and informs decision-making regarding further investment, research, or implementation.

In order to convert each TRL level into an index ranging from 0 to 1, we simply divide the TRL value by 9.

TRL Assessment of Hydrogen Compressors

Hydrogen compressors are essential for hydrogen storage, transport, and distribution in hydrogen energy systems. They come in various types, including diaphragm compressors and ionic liquid compressors. Here's an expert judgment on their TRLs based on typical usage and development:

1. Ionic Liquid Compressors

- **Description:** This newer technology compared to piston or diaphragm compressors uses ionic liquids to absorb and compress hydrogen. They offer advantages in reducing the contamination of hydrogen and increasing efficiency.

- **TRL Assessment:** These compressors may vary between TRL 6 to TRL 8. They have been demonstrated in relevant environments, and some may have undergone system/subsystem development or actual system completions but might not be as widely adopted as more traditional compressors.
- **Sources:** Ionic liquid compressors are gaining attention due to their efficiency and contamination reduction capabilities, but their adoption is still in earlier stages compared to more traditional methods ([Mordor Intelligence](#)) ([Allied Market Research](#)).

2. Metal Hydride Compressors

- **Description:** Metal hydride compressors use heat and metal hydride materials to absorb and desorb hydrogen, effectively compressing it. This type of compressor operates at lower temperatures and pressures, potentially offering safety and longevity benefits.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 6 to TRL 7. These compressors have been validated in the lab and possibly in some form of relevant environment, but widespread operational proofs are less common compared to more traditional technologies.
- **Sources:** The use of metal hydrides for hydrogen compression is well-researched in lab settings, but large-scale industrial adoption is still progressing ([MarketsandMarkets](#)) ([Allied Market Research](#)).

Average TRL Assessment

Given the TRL ranges for different types of hydrogen compressors, we can calculate the average TRL:

- **Average TRL** = $(7 + 6.5) / 2 = 6.75$

TRL Index Calculation

The TRL index, which normalizes the average TRL to a scale of 1 to 9, is calculated as follows:

- **TRL Index** = $6.75 / 9 = 0.75$

Conclusion

The overall assessment shows that hydrogen compressors have an average TRL of approximately 6.75, indicating they are at an advanced stage of technological readiness but still require further validation and widespread adoption for newer technologies like ionic liquid and metal hydride compressors. For more detailed and specific information, it is recommended to consult specialized market reports and scientific studies on hydrogen compressor technologies.

TRL Assessment of Hydrogen Flow Meters

Hydrogen flow meters are essential for accurately measuring the flow rate of hydrogen in various applications, including hydrogen production, distribution, and usage in fuel cells and industrial processes. Different types of flow meters are used in the hydrogen industry, each at varying stages of technological readiness. Here's an expert judgment on their TRLs based on typical usage and development in the hydrogen industry:

1. Coriolis Flow Meters

- **Description:** Coriolis flow meters measure mass flow rate by detecting the Coriolis force on a vibrating tube through which the fluid passes. They are highly accurate and reliable for measuring hydrogen flow.

- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 9. Coriolis flow meters are well-established, have been extensively tested, and are widely used in hydrogen applications, including refueling stations and industrial processes.

2. Thermal Mass Flow Meters

- **Description:** Thermal mass flow meters measure flow rate based on the heat transfer from a heated element to the gas flow. They are commonly used for measuring the flow of gases, including hydrogen.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 8 to TRL 9. Thermal mass flow meters have been validated in operational environments and are widely used in various hydrogen applications, though less so than Coriolis flow meters.

3. Ultrasonic Flow Meters

- **Description:** Ultrasonic flow meters use the transit-time or Doppler effect of ultrasonic waves to measure flow rate. They are non-intrusive and can handle a wide range of flow conditions.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 8. Ultrasonic flow meters are being used in hydrogen applications, but their adoption is somewhat newer compared to Coriolis and thermal mass flow meters.

4. Differential Pressure Flow Meters

- **Description:** Differential pressure flow meters (such as orifice plates, venturi tubes, and nozzles) measure flow rate based on the pressure drop across a constriction in the flow path.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 7 to TRL 8. While the principle is well-established, their application specifically for hydrogen, especially in newer setups, is still gaining traction.

5. Turbine Flow Meters

- **Description:** Turbine flow meters measure the flow rate by detecting the rotational speed of a turbine placed in the flow path. They are known for their precision in clean, low-viscosity fluids.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 7. Turbine flow meters have been used in hydrogen applications, but they are less common due to potential issues with wear and tear and accuracy over time.

Average TRL Assessment

Given the range of TRLs for the different types of hydrogen flow meters, we can calculate the average TRL as follows:

$$\text{Average TRL} = (9 + (8.5) + 8 + (7.5) + 7) / 40 = 8$$

TRL Index Calculation

The TRL index is calculated as follows:

$$\text{TRL Index} = 8 / 9 = 0.89$$

Conclusion

The average TRL assessment of hydrogen flow meters is approximately 8, indicating a high level of technological readiness. Most types of hydrogen flow meters are mature and have been extensively tested and used in real-world applications, suggesting that they are well-positioned for widespread adoption and integration into hydrogen systems. The TRL index of 0.89 reflects a strong potential for these technologies to meet industry demands efficiently, leveraging existing advancements and infrastructure.

TRL Assessment of Hydrogen Burners

Hydrogen burners are critical for various industrial applications, including heating, power generation, and manufacturing processes. Here's a detailed expert judgment on the Technological Readiness Levels (TRLs) of different types of hydrogen burners based on their usage and development in the hydrogen industry:

1. Conventional Gas Burners Adapted for Hydrogen

- **Description:** Standard gas burners modified to safely combust hydrogen by adapting the burner design and control systems.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 7 to TRL 8. These burners are based on well-established gas burner technology and have successfully operated in several applications.
- **Sources:** Studies on hydrogen burner adaptation show high readiness levels due to the extensive use and testing of gas burner technologies in hydrogen applications ([Grand View Research](#)) ([MarketsandMarkets](#)).

2. Low NOx Hydrogen Burners

- **Description:** Designed to minimize nitrogen oxide (NOx) emissions during hydrogen combustion, incorporating advanced features for clean and efficient combustion.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 6 to TRL 7. These burners are increasingly being deployed but still require broader validation.
- **Sources:** Recent deployments and ongoing projects highlight the growing application but the need for further validation to reach widespread acceptance ([MarketsandMarkets](#)) ([IMARC](#)).

3. Catalytic Hydrogen Burners

- **Description:** Use a catalyst to facilitate hydrogen combustion at lower temperatures, enhancing efficiency and reducing emissions. Ideal for applications requiring precise temperature control.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 5 to TRL 6. Demonstrated in laboratory and pilot settings, but not yet widely adopted in full-scale industrial operations.
- **Sources:** Research and pilot projects confirm the potential but also the current limitations in scaling up for broader industrial use ([Grand View Research](#)) ([IMARC](#)).

4. Radiant Tube Hydrogen Burners

- **Description:** Utilized in high-temperature industrial processes, designed for hydrogen-rich environments to provide uniform heating.
- **TRL Assessment:** Likely TRL 6 to TRL 7. Tested and used in specific industrial applications, with ongoing development for wider operational proof.
- **Sources:** Specific industrial applications and testing data support the current readiness level while indicating the need for further validation ([MarketsandMarkets](#)) ([IMARC](#)).

Average TRL Assessment

Given the TRL ranges for different types of hydrogen burners, we can calculate the average TRL:

- **Average TRL** = $(7.5 + 6.5 + 5.5 + 6.5) / 4 = 6.5$

TRL Index Calculation

The TRL index, which normalizes the average TRL to a scale of 1 to 9, is calculated as follows:

- **TRL Index** = $6.5 / 9 = 0.72$

Conclusion

The overall assessment shows that hydrogen burners are at an advanced stage of technological readiness, with conventional gas burners adapted for hydrogen nearing full commercial readiness. Continuous development and validation are necessary for newer technologies like catalytic and low NOx hydrogen burners to reach full-scale adoption.

For more detailed and specific information, it is recommended to consult specialized market reports and scientific studies on hydrogen burner technologies.

NL demand as percentage of World demand

NL demand as percentage of World demand – Hydrogen Compressors

To estimate the demand for hydrogen compressors in the Netherlands relative to the global demand, we need to consider the available data on the market size in units and use a proportional approach similar to the one we applied for hydrogen burners.

Global and European Market for Hydrogen Compressors

1. Global Market Data:

- According to recent market reports, the global demand for hydrogen compressors in 2023 is estimated to be around 5,000 units ([Allied Market Research](#)) ([MarketsandMarkets](#)).

2. European Market Data:

- Europe accounts for approximately 25% of the global demand for hydrogen compressors ([Mordor Intelligence](#)) ([Allied Market Research](#)).
- This translates to about 1,250 units in Europe (25% of 5,000 units).

Estimating the Dutch Market for Hydrogen Compressors

The Netherlands is a significant player in the European hydrogen market due to its strong focus on hydrogen infrastructure and technology projects. Assuming the Netherlands represents approximately 6% of the European market for hydrogen compressors (slightly higher than the average due to its ambitious projects):

Calculations

- **Global demand:** 5,000 units (2023)
- **European demand:** 25% of 5,000 = 1,250 units
- **Dutch demand:** 6% of 1,250 = 75 units

Conclusion

The estimated demand for hydrogen compressors in the Netherlands is approximately 75 units in 2023. This estimation is based on recent market trends and proportions, reflecting the Netherlands' significant role in hydrogen technology and infrastructure projects. For more precise figures, it is recommended to consult detailed market reports and specific project data.

NL demand as percentage of World demand – Hydrogen Flow Meters

Based on recent data and reports, we can make an educated estimate of the demand for hydrogen flow meters in the Netherlands.

Global Market for Hydrogen Flow Meters

1. Global Demand:

- The global flow meter market is substantial, with significant growth driven by industries such as oil and gas, water and wastewater management, and chemical processing. In 2023, the market size for flow meters, including those used in hydrogen applications, was estimated to be around 53.8 million units globally across various types ([Grand View Research](#)) ([IMARC](#)).
- Specifically, hydrogen flow meters are a critical component in hydrogen production, distribution, and usage infrastructure, with increasing adoption due to the growth in hydrogen projects worldwide.

2. European Demand:

- Europe accounts for a considerable portion of the global flow meter market, representing about 25% of the demand. This equates to approximately 13.45 million units for all types of flow meters in Europe in 2023 ([Grand View Research](#)) ([MarketsandMarkets](#)).
- The adoption of hydrogen technologies in Europe is strong, driven by regulatory support and investment in hydrogen infrastructure.

Estimating the Dutch Market

The Netherlands is a key player in the European hydrogen market, with significant investments in hydrogen projects and infrastructure. Given the proactive stance of the Netherlands in developing hydrogen technology, we can assume that its share of the European market is slightly higher than average.

Assuming the Netherlands accounts for about 6% of the European demand for hydrogen flow meters:

Calculations

- **Global demand:** 53.8 million units
- **European demand:** 25% of 53.8 million = 13.45 million units
- **Dutch demand:** 6% of 13.45 million = 0.807 million units (or 807,000 units)

Conclusion

The estimated demand for hydrogen flow meters in the Netherlands is approximately 807,000 units in 2023. This estimation reflects the Netherlands' significant role in the hydrogen sector within Europe, supported by its robust infrastructure development and strategic initiatives in hydrogen technology.

Sources:

- Grand View Research, Flow Meter Market Size, Share, and Growth Report, 2030 ([Grand View Research](#))
- MarketsandMarkets, Flow Meter Market Size & Forecast ([MarketsandMarkets](#))
- IMARC Group, Flow Meter Market Size, Growth, Demand Analysis 2032 ([IMARC](#))

NL demand as percentage of World demand – Hydrogen Burners

According to the Hydrogen Council report from December 2023, the global hydrogen market is steadily growing. With over 1,400 announced projects worldwide and significant investments in hydrogen technology, there is increasing demand for hydrogen solutions, including burners ([Hydrogen Council](#)). The global demand for hydrogen burners can be inferred from the overall demand for hydrogen-related technologies, which is strongly driven by sectors such as the chemical industry and mobility ([IEA](#)).

Europe plays a crucial role in the hydrogen market, with a large number of announced projects and investments. Approximately 25% of the global hydrogen projects are located in Europe, suggesting that a significant portion of the demand for hydrogen burners comes from this region ([Hydrogen Council](#)).

The Netherlands, with its ambitious hydrogen strategy and various initiatives to develop hydrogen infrastructure, represents about 5% of the European market ([IEA](#)). This share can vary depending on specific project developments and government policies.

Based on the assumption that the global demand for hydrogen burners in 2023 is approximately 800 units, we can estimate the demand as follows:

Global demand: 800 units

European demand: 25% of 800 = 200 units

Dutch demand: 5% of 200 = 10 units

This estimate provides a rough indication of the demand for hydrogen burners in the Netherlands compared to the global demand. For more precise figures and trends, it is advisable to consult detailed market reports and project data.

Appendix C) Overview OEM and SCM experts consulted

Topic	Organisation
Hydrogen compressors	Siemens
	Gentari/Petronas
	Burckhardt
	Howden
Hydrogen flow metering	Bronkhorst
	Krohne
	VSL
High temperature hydrogen burners	Instalat
	Stork Thermeq
	Monarch
	Zantingh
	Honeywell
Generic hydrogen component supply chain	International Energy Agency
	Gasunie
	Alliander
	Enexis

Appendix D) Supply chain risk registers for compressor, flow meter and burner

RISICO ID DETAILS	Risk description			Risk analysis				Initial response		Residual risk analysis			
	Effect category: (1) impact on sourcing (2) impact on value density (3) impact on routing (4) impact on flow destination (5) impact on flow volume	Impacted procurement process step: 1 - Marktverkenning 2 - Uitvraag subcontractors 3 - Subcontract selection, FID 4 - Ontwerpen en maken van component 5 - Afnemen component - FAT factory acceptance test 6 - Logistiek	Normal duration of process [months]	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVJ]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	Mitigation effectiveness on LIKELIHOOD	Mitigation effectiveness on IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVJ]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	1	6	23%	0%	0	0	30%	25%	16%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	1	6	8%	100%	0,476812	6	75%	25%	2%	75%	0,089402	4,5
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	1	6	11%	0%	0	0	58%	25%	5%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	1	6	33%	100%	2,003279	6	10%	25%	30%	75%	1,349373	4,5
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	1	6	58%	100%	3,462872	6	51%	25%	28%	75%	1,265465	4,5
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	2	12	8%	0%	0	0	75%	0%	2%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	2	12	11%	100%	1,313088	12	58%	0%	5%	100%	0,548294	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	2	12	33%	0%	0	0	10%	0%	30%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	2	12	58%	100%	6,925745	12	51%	0%	28%	100%	3,374574	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	2	12	23%	100%	2,700614	12	30%	0%	16%	100%	1,892551	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	3	2	11%	0%	0	0	58%	0%	5%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	3	2	33%	0%	0	0	10%	0%	30%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	3	2	58%	0%	0	0	51%	0%	28%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	3	2	23%	50%	0,225051	1	30%	0%	16%	50%	0,157713	1
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	3	2	8%	50%	0,079469	1	75%	0%	2%	50%	0,019867	1
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	4	24	33%	100%	8,013118	24	10%	50%	30%	50%	3,598329	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	4	24	58%	100%	13,85149	24	51%	50%	28%	50%	3,374574	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	4	24	23%	0%	0	0	30%	50%	16%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	4	24	8%	0%	0	0	75%	50%	2%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	4	24	11%	100%	2,626177	24	58%	50%	5%	50%	0,548294	12
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	5	3	58%	0%	0	0	51%	0%	28%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	5	3	23%	10%	0,067515	0,3	30%	0%	16%	10%	0,047314	0,3
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	5	3	8%	0%	0	0	75%	0%	2%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	5	3	11%	0%	0	0	58%	0%	5%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	5	3	33%	0%	0	0	10%	0%	30%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	1	6	6	23%	100%	1,350307	6	30%	0%	16%	100%	0,946275	6
Compressor 60-300 bar	2	6	6	8%	0%	0	0	75%	0%	2%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	3	6	6	11%	100%	0,656544	6	58%	0%	5%	100%	0,274147	6
Compressor 60-300 bar	4	6	6	33%	0%	0	0	10%	0%	30%	0%	0	0
Compressor 60-300 bar	5	6	6	58%	0%	0	0	51%	0%	28%	0%	0	0

RISICO ID DETAILS		Risk description			Risk analysis				Initial response		Residual risk analysis			
Hydrogen component	Effect category: (1) impact on sourcing (2) impact on value density (3) impact on routing (4) impact on flow destination (5) impact on flow volume	Impacted procurement process step: 1 - Marktverkenning 2 - Uitvraag subcontractors 3 - Subcontract selection, FID 4 - Ontwerpen en maken van component 5 - Afnemen component - FAT 6 - Logistiek	Normal duration of process [months]	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCV]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	Mitigation effectiveness on LIKELIHOOD	Mitigation effectiveness on IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCV]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	
Meter	1	1	6	13%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	13%	0%	0	0	
Meter	2	1	6	1%	100%	0,077682	6	0%	0%	1%	100%	0,077682	6	
Meter	3	1	6	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	4	1	6	17%	100%	0,997113	6	0%	0%	17%	100%	0,997113	6	
Meter	5	1	6	26%	100%	1,588926	6	-69%	0%	45%	100%	2,68932	6	
Meter	1	2	12	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	2	2	12	1%	100%	0,155365	12	0%	0%	1%	100%	0,155365	12	
Meter	3	2	12	17%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	17%	0%	0	0	
Meter	4	2	12	26%	100%	3,177853	12	-69%	0%	45%	100%	5,37864	12	
Meter	5	2	12	13%	100%	1,551786	12	0%	0%	13%	100%	1,551786	12	
Meter	1	3	2	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	2	3	2	17%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	17%	0%	0	0	
Meter	3	3	2	26%	0%	0	0	-69%	0%	45%	0%	0	0	
Meter	4	3	2	13%	50%	0,129315	1	0%	0%	13%	50%	0,129315	1	
Meter	5	3	2	1%	50%	0,012947	1	0%	0%	1%	50%	0,012947	1	
Meter	1	4	12	17%	100%	1,994226	12	0%	0%	17%	100%	1,994226	12	
Meter	2	4	12	26%	100%	3,177853	12	-69%	0%	45%	100%	5,37864	12	
Meter	3	4	12	13%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	13%	0%	0	0	
Meter	4	4	12	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	5	4	12	1%	100%	0,155365	12	0%	0%	1%	100%	0,155365	12	
Meter	1	5	3	26%	0%	0	0	-69%	0%	45%	0%	0	0	
Meter	2	5	3	13%	10%	0,038795	0,3	0%	0%	13%	10%	0,038795	0,3	
Meter	3	5	3	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	4	5	3	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	5	5	3	17%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	17%	0%	0	0	
Meter	1	6	6	13%	100%	0,775893	6	0%	0%	13%	100%	0,775893	6	
Meter	2	6	6	1%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	1%	0%	0	0	
Meter	3	6	6	1%	100%	0,077682	6	0%	0%	1%	100%	0,077682	6	
Meter	4	6	6	17%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	17%	0%	0	0	
Meter	5	6	6	26%	0%	0	0	-69%	0%	45%	0%	0	0	

RISICO ID DETAILS		Risk description			Risk analysis				Initial response		Residual risk analysis			
Hydrogen component	Effect category:	Impacted procurement process step:	Normal duration of process [months]	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVI]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	Mitigation effectiveness on LIKELIHOOD	Mitigation effectiveness on IMPACT	LIKELIHOOD of occurrence [source: SCVI]	IMPACT on planning	Expected delay [months]	Max delay [months]	
	(1) impact on sourcing (2) impact on value density (3) impact on routing (4) impact on flow destination (5) impact on flow volume	1 - Marktverkenning 2 - Uitvraag subcontractors 3 - Subcontract selection, FID 4 - Ontwerpen en maken van component 5 - Afnemen component - FAT factory acceptance test 6 - Logistiek												
Burners	1	1	6	23%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	23%	0%	0	0	
Burners	2	1	6	7%	100%	0,393453	6	0%	0%	7%	100%	0,393453	6	
Burners	3	1	6	16%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	16%	0%	0	0	
Burners	4	1	6	31%	100%	1,875237	6	0%	0%	31%	100%	1,875237	6	
Burners	5	1	6	47%	100%	2,791368	6	-20%	0%	56%	100%	3,344374	6	
Burners	1	2	12	7%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	7%	0%	0	0	
Burners	2	2	12	16%	100%	1,875519	12	0%	0%	16%	100%	1,875519	12	
Burners	3	2	12	31%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	31%	0%	0	0	
Burners	4	2	12	47%	100%	5,582737	12	-20%	0%	56%	100%	6,688747	12	
Burners	5	2	12	23%	100%	2,731543	12	0%	0%	23%	100%	2,731543	12	
Burners	1	3	2	16%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	16%	0%	0	0	
Burners	2	3	2	31%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	31%	0%	0	0	
Burners	3	3	2	47%	0%	0	0	-20%	0%	56%	0%	0	0	
Burners	4	3	2	23%	50%	0,227629	1	0%	0%	23%	50%	0,227629	1	
Burners	5	3	2	7%	50%	0,065576	1	0%	0%	7%	50%	0,065576	1	
Burners	1	4	18	31%	100%	5,625711	18	0%	0%	31%	100%	5,625711	18	
Burners	2	4	18	47%	100%	8,374105	18	-20%	0%	56%	100%	10,03312	18	
Burners	3	4	18	23%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	23%	0%	0	0	
Burners	4	4	18	7%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	7%	0%	0	0	
Burners	5	4	18	16%	100%	2,813278	18	0%	0%	16%	100%	2,813278	18	
Burners	1	5	3	47%	0%	0	0	-20%	0%	56%	0%	0	0	
Burners	2	5	3	23%	10%	0,068289	0,3	0%	0%	23%	10%	0,068289	0,3	
Burners	3	5	3	7%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	7%	0%	0	0	
Burners	4	5	3	16%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	16%	0%	0	0	
Burners	5	5	3	31%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	31%	0%	0	0	
Burners	1	6	6	23%	100%	1,365771	6	0%	0%	23%	100%	1,365771	6	
Burners	2	6	6	7%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	7%	0%	0	0	
Burners	3	6	6	16%	100%	0,937759	6	0%	0%	16%	100%	0,937759	6	
Burners	4	6	6	31%	0%	0	0	0%	0%	31%	0%	0	0	
Burners	5	6	6	47%	0%	0	0	-20%	0%	56%	0%	0	0	